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ABSTRACT

Conspiracism is a worldview defined by one or more conspiracy theories, usually with a tendency to perceive new events as intrinsically conspiratorial. After examining various factors in the formation and effects of a conspiracist worldview, this master's thesis investigates the impact of conspiracism upon extremist ideologies and organizations within American society, including radicalization, recruitment, and military veteran involvement. It recommends a new, education-based approach to mitigating conspiracism within the United States Army to help prevent future extremism while better educating the overall force. It ultimately suggests that focused instruction in subjects such as political science, international relations theory, economics, history, and government administration, combined with enhanced training in critical-thinking and reasoning skills, may provide individuals with the tools necessary to prevent the adoption of the Manichean worldview typically found in conspiracy-theory-based extremism.

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PREFACE:
YOU REALLY SHOULD READ THIS

I love a good story. In my adolescence, I devoured Time-Life's *Mysteries of the Unknown* and watched every episode of the X-files. I hoped that alien creatures had really crashed in Roswell, and I wanted to bend spoons with my mind. Fox Mulder told me that the truth is out there, but Mr. "Neo" Anderson was wrong—there is a spoon, and it's especially resilient to my mental control. As I got older, the mystery began to fade and the world became increasingly boring. I gave religious dedication a try, but my devotion to understanding the scriptures produced an unintended result—the more I learned, the less I believed. It became apparent that reality simply wasn't as exciting as I had originally thought, then the World Trade Center buildings collapsed on September 11th (9/11) and things significantly changed.

I was new to my team at 3rd Special Forces Group (Airborne) the first time I heard that 9/11 was an inside job. It sounded quite ridiculous at first, but the documentary *Loose Change* (2005) made some interesting points. Before I knew it, I was chest deep in the Moon landing hoax, the Sovereign Citizens' anti-tax propaganda, the secret world of the global elites in the "New World Order," and the plan to intern citizens in Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) death camps across the United States. I must humbly admit, some of it was rather convincing.

Many people scoff at conspiracy theorists, but oftentimes that's because they haven't actually listened to what conspiracists have to say. Most modern conspiracy theories adopt the guise of credible scholarship, and the Internet is filled with sites dedicated to making that "research" available to anyone willing to see it. They do their homework. In the past, I too have fallen victim to some of their traps. Anyone with a

similar love of mystery or longing for truth would likely to do the same. That's what traps are for—and they can be dangerous. Some would have you believe that the government is merely guilty of an alien cover-up, but others claim that it conducts false-flag attacks against its own people. One version is likely to end with a petition for disclosure. The other could lead to guerrilla warfare.

During my almost twelve years in the US Army, I've witnessed the full spectrum of military conspiracy theorists. From the casual dabbler to the dedicated evangelist, believers are quite common amongst our ranks. Service members are, after all, normal people, and conspiracy theories have become a hallmark of American culture. There is nothing wrong with belief in conspiracy theories *per se*, but when such belief starts to push a person's worldview towards one that defines governments and institutions as "evil," I start to get worried—especially when that person is trained in the art of war. I know how easy it can be to get caught up in the propaganda because I've actually read it myself. As a soldier, there's an amazingly strong level of cognitive dissonance that comes from even basic exposure to some of the arguments. I can't imagine how it feels to become a true believer.

Conspiracism cannot be described as uncommon. It is prevalent. Anyone who dares to read the comments section to almost any major news article on the Internet will quickly become an expert on the latest conspiracy theories. Those with the courage to dive into websites like *Above Top Secret*, *Prison Planet*, or *Godlike Productions* will find out just how influential those conspiracy theories can be. The presence of military-veteran believers will also become readily apparent, but you don't need to frequent the

specialty websites to see them in action. They post conspiracy-inspired comments to news articles and share conspiracist propaganda on social media all of the time.

In the military we're taught to be critical thinkers—or so we are told. While a student in basic, advanced, and specialty courses, I never received formal critical-thinking training. What I know about logical fallacies I learned on my own. When I instructed the Warrior, Advanced, and Senior Leader courses for Special Forces, we talked about critical thinking as if it was our life-style. We never actually formally taught it. My critical thinking, logic, and reasoning training came mainly from self-study, and I'm beginning to suspect that they might be perishable skills. I love a good story as long as it makes sense. And conspiracy theories make great stories—until they don't make any sense. At that point they begin the transition from fact to fiction. For some people that crucial transition never occurs because they lack a frame of reference to falsify the theories—or at least to realize that the theories aren't all they're cracked up to be.

I chose to write this thesis to help others, especially my brothers-and-sisters-in-arms, to build a robust frame of reference. My goal isn't to denounce conspiracy theories or the people who believe them. It's good to question the motivations of those in positions of power, but reality isn't the black-and-white world of good-versus-evil that some make it out to be. That's my concern. That type of mentality can lead to the forfeiture of political activism in exchange for violent behavior. I think we can all agree that's not a good idea. Hopefully this small contribution will provide some perspective—and maybe even contribute to a solution for curbing extremism through non-violent means. Personally, I think that's a great idea.

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

Conspiracy theories are nothing new. They seem to be the result of evolutionary adaptations inherent to human psychology. They are also artifacts of social, religious, and cultural institutions. They might even be natural by-products of political systems, but they definitely play a role in all of the above. Conspiracy theories can be found in religious, political, and social narratives around the globe, and they date back to the beginnings of written history. In America, conspiracy theories have become commonplace. From the Salem Witch trials and the Red Scares to the “New World Order,”¹ they have played a crucial role in creating subcultures of fear and an overall tendency toward conspiracism within the American psyche.² They also provide fertile breeding ground for extremist ideologies. Conspiracy theories feed the Manichean belief systems commonly found in extremist groups, and they can become the catalysts for violent action.³ They have even provided a common enemy to unite seemingly disparate terrorist organizations. Simply stated, conspiracism paints the world in black and white.

The most commonly believed conspiracy theories are based on perceptions of elitism, political or social power construction, international economics, and government administration. Many extremist organizations, including most American right-wing

1. “New World Order” conspiracy theorists believe that a powerful elite group strives to control the world and its governments. Different variations of the conspiracy theory exist, ranging from Jewish plots for world domination to United Nations plans to destroy US sovereignty.

2. Oliver and Wood (2014) define *conspiracism* as “widespread belief in conspiracy theories” (953). Hodapp and Von Kannon (2008) define it as an expansion of theory to become “an entire philosophy ... a way of viewing the world” (10). This paper combines aspects of both definitions to define conspiracism as “a worldview defined by one or more conspiracy theories (usually with a tendency to perceive new events as intrinsically conspiratorial).” See Skoll and Korstanje (2013) for an analysis of the American fear culture.

3. Manichean ideologies define world events in terms of good versus evil. See Chapter 3 for a more in-depth discussion on Manichean beliefs.

groups, base their ideologies on a mixture of religious and conspiracist ideas that—when combined—can and often do lead to violence.⁴ Historically, right-wing extremist groups within the United States have enjoyed heavy military-veteran membership, and their military members have provided substantial technical, tactical, and leadership expertise.⁵ Today, several movements actively recruit veterans and law enforcement officials for their skills and knowledge. Such groups spread targeted, well-made, conspiracy-theory-based propaganda through print, media, and the Internet. The conspiracy theories they promote saturate the media at large, affecting not only the psychology of Americans, but also that of the rest of the world. International terrorist organizations have even been known to recycle and propagate anti-American conspiracy theories that originated in the United States itself.

With conspiracism widespread throughout American culture, combating extremist propaganda can be problematic. Overt attacks on the conspiracy theories themselves tend to merely legitimize them in the minds of believers.⁶ Calling such believers ignorant, insane, or paranoid only reinforces any existing feeling of alienation, which is already a factor that can lead to conspiracist ideation to begin with.⁷ A more effective way to defeat the conspiracist mentality may be through better-focused education. Victims of conspiracism often lack the tools necessary to think their way out of its fallacious reasoning. Many come from modest economic and social backgrounds and are absent the

4. See Chapter 5 for details about how conspiracism can lead to violent behavior.

5. For the purposes of this paper, the term *veteran* will be used to describe both former and current members of the US military.

6. The act of denying or debunking conspiracy theories can become supporting evidence for a cover-up in the minds of believers (Bartlett and Miller 2010, 5; Jolley 2013, 37).

7. See Leman and Cinnirella (2013, 7–8) for studies showing a correlation between feelings of alienation and belief in conspiracy theories.

experience, exposure, or education needed to unpack conspiracy-theory propaganda. They simply cannot comprehend the true complexity of political, social, and economic realities because they lack sufficient narrative. Conspiracists therefore reduce the world's complexity to fit unrealistic models that are easier for them to understand. Conspiracy theories provide them with the simplified framework to do so. Additionally, the human thinking process is prone to false pattern recognition, which tends to make conspiracy theories appear more credible.⁸ Supplying access to the right information, through focused education in combination with enhanced critical-thinking and reasoning skills, may be enough to break the spell.

As the United States Army transitions to an education-based force—and given the history of veteran involvement in extremist organizations—military training could serve as an excellent venue for an education-based approach for combating extremism.⁹ The Army's current critical-thinking training focuses predominantly on battlefield or operational readiness and mission planning. It does not teach soldiers to deal with the logical fallacies and faulty reasoning intrinsic to most conspiracy theories. Although the Army encourages higher education, soldiers are not required to take courses in economics, political science, history, or international relations, all of which would provide a framework with which to analyze the conspiracy theories most frequently used to justify extremism. By implementing a curriculum that includes focused instruction on such subjects, combined with enhanced critical-thinking training, the Army's

8. See Chapter 5 for information on human hierarchical thinking and false pattern recognition.

9. The *Army Leader Development Strategy* (DA 2013) states: "The Army is expanding and encouraging a broad range of assignment opportunities in academia, interagency, and multinational settings to prepare leaders for a complex and uncertain operational environment" (8). Additionally the Army has implemented a new learner-centric model for classroom instruction (DA 2011).

professional development programs could better educate the overall force and simultaneously mitigate current and future veteran extremism. Additionally, the Army's Threat Awareness and Reporting Program (TARP) concentrates on identifying possible extremists but does not fully address their recruitment strategies.¹⁰ Better education and critical-thinking training could possibly do both.

Defining Conspiracism: Conspiracies, Theories, and Worldviews

For most people, the term “conspiracy theory” conjures images of tin foil hats, alien abductions, or Russell Crowe's portrayal of the paranoid schizophrenic mathematician, John Nash, in the movie *A Beautiful Mind* (2001). Reality, however, tells a different story. Conspiracy theories range from the seemingly mundane to the highly fantastical. They can be totally believable or completely ridiculous. Sometimes they are absolutely true. Often times they are utterly false. They appear frequently in literature, film, oral traditions, and even history books. Though conspiracy theories are quite common, to understand them it is essential to first define the term conspiracy itself.

In legal terms, a *conspiracy* is an “an agreement between two or more persons to commit an illegal or unlawful act or to achieve a legal act but by illegal or unlawful means.”¹¹ President John F. Kennedy's administration conspired with the Central Intelligence Agency (CIA) to assassinate Fidel Castro during the Cold War (Herring 2011, 707), and Martha Stewart used insider knowledge in an attempt to save money before her stocks fell (“Stewart Convicted on all Charges” 2004). These kinds of conspiracies do exist, and abuses of power are not uncommon. In fact, one could argue

10. See Army Regulation 381-12, *Threat Awareness and Reporting Program* (DA 2010) and Chapter 6 for more details.

11. See <http://conspiracy.uslegal.com> for an explanation of both criminal and civil conspiracies.

that conspiracy is a pervasive strategic tool, especially in matters of politics and defense. Furthermore, conspiracies are not limited to illegal activities.¹² They are, quite frankly, a universal part of the human experience.¹³

Conspiracies, whether true or false, come in different shapes and sizes. In this particular discussion, the emphasis lies on the *type* of conspiracy, not the explanation for it. In his book, *A Culture of Conspiracy: Apocalyptic Visions in Contemporary America* (2003, 6), political science professor Michael Barkun, PhD, categorizes conspiracies in three ways: event conspiracies, systemic conspiracies, and superconspiracies. Event conspiracies, such as those mentioned in the preceding paragraph, are limited to singular events or series of events orchestrated by individuals or small groups for very specific, localized purposes. In most cases, the legal definition of conspiracy sufficiently defines event conspiracies. Systemic conspiracies, on the other hand, are conspiracies of a much larger scale in which a group or organization seeks to infiltrate, subvert, or control whole countries, regions or even the entire world. Much of the anti-communist propaganda of the early Cold War painted communism as a systemic conspiracy by claiming that the Communists' ultimate goals were to destroy religion and conquer the world.¹⁴ Superconspiracies combine elements of event and systemic conspiracies into an

12. Uscinski, Parent, and Torres (2011) argue that “when Democrats are in power, the right will vilify the left with conspiracy theories, and when Republicans are in power, the left will demonize the right in reciprocal fashion” (32).

13. In his guide to critical thinking, neurologist and skeptic Steven Novella, MD (2013), asserts, “we all have a little conspiracy theorist hiding inside each of us” (Chapter 19, 26:28–26:41).

14. Historian Dianne Kirby, PhD (2013) points out that the Soviets were not necessarily anti-religious, but rather non-religious, and actively rallied religious support to defeat the Nazis (9:55–12:30). Whether Communists did or did not persecute religions is not the point. Communism came in different flavors, each with different goals specific to individual regions, and many communist players had different ideas about how communism should be implemented. Anti-communist propaganda, however, portrayed all types of communism as a systemic conspiracy because it presented communism as if it were controlled and orchestrated by a single group with the same goal: to destroy religion.

overarching centralized network in which multiple conspiracies link together as part of a complex hierarchy. In Superconspiracies, master conspirators control and manipulate lesser conspirators who may or may not be aware of their role within the larger conspiracy. David Icke's claim that malevolent aliens from another planet secretly control the world's governments through interconnected ideological, social, and political conspiracies is a prime example of a superconspiracy (Barkun 2003, Chapters 5–6).

Neurologist and skeptic Steven Novella, MD (2013), describes a fourth type of conspiracy, the grand conspiracy, which seems to contain elements of the other three. Grand conspiracies require significant coordination between many individuals across multiple organizations. While systemic and superconspiracies are unlikely to be true and typically come with nefarious labels, grand conspiracies do not necessarily follow that pattern. The Manhattan Project, for example, exemplifies a grand conspiracy that is both true and usually understood as justified.¹⁵

By definition, each type of conspiracy, from the smallest to the largest, requires a cadre of insiders working towards a goal. The term *conspiracy theory*, then, should be easy to define. It is not. In his doctoral dissertation (2012), philosopher Matthew Dentith, PhD, uses more than 30 pages to narrow down the definition of conspiracy theory. The feat is quite substantial because—as professor Juha Räikkä, PhD (2009), points out—when conspiracy theories become accepted explanations they are no longer considered “theories.” They have instead become “official wisdom” (187). *Conspiracy theory*, therefore, implies something unconventional or out of the norm. Unconventional or abnormal, however, does not equate to wrong, implausible, or crazy—just alternative.

15. The US government was able to conceal the production of the first atomic bomb, which required massive coordination and secrecy across many individuals and groups, qualifying the Manhattan Project as a grand conspiracy.

Most people, though, do not normally think of conspiracy theories as simply “alternative.” They come with a certain connotation that is hard to define, but everyone seems to know it “when they see it” (Brotherton 2013, 9). Conspiracy Theories are typically described as crazy, paranoid, or delusional. The negative stigma is a result of the fact that conspiracy theories usually do not provide the most plausible or believable explanations. They defiantly stand in the face of better evidence, yet believers wholeheartedly accept their claims. Academics have proposed psychological, philosophical, sociological, and political explanations for belief in conspiracy theories, but no single discipline sufficiently explains the phenomenon.¹⁶

Recognizing that *conspiracy theory* comes with baggage attached, we can define it as “a proposed explanation of historical events which cites as a main causal factor, a small group of powerful persons (the conspirators) acting in secret for their own benefit” (Uscinski, Parent, and Torres 2011, 6). Conspiracy theories seem more concerned about the *cui bono* question than the actual event they seek to explain.¹⁷ The sense of realization that comes with “figuring it out” can profoundly affect a conspiracist’s worldview.¹⁸ Belief in a conspiracy theory, however, is not grounds for immediate concern. One person may believe that the Moon landing was a hoax perpetrated by the US government, but at the same time understand it as a necessary strategy for winning the Space Race during the Cold War. Another person might interpret the same conspiracy as evidence for government corruption aimed at exploiting the American population. Either

16. See Chapter 2 for details about the various approaches to understanding belief in conspiracy theories.

17. *Cui bono* is Latin for “to whose benefit?” The *cui bono* question seeks to explain an event by determining who actually benefits from its occurrence.

18. This paper defines *conspiracist* as “someone who believes in one or more conspiracy theories despite better evidence.”

way, it is not necessary for the conspiracist to jump to conclusions about nefarious shadow governments or evil societies that secretly control the world. Belief in conspiracy theories *per se* does not necessarily lead to extreme worldviews. Those who do make such Manichean connections, however, are more vulnerable to extremist recruitment. They could also be more prone to violence.¹⁹ Conspiracy-theory believers develop a tendency toward further conspiracist ideation, meaning they interpret new events, patterns, or systems as intrinsically conspiratorial. This paper therefore, focuses not on conspiracy theories themselves but rather on conspiracism—a worldview defined by conspiracy theories—because the black-and-white perspective conspiracism creates can drive believers toward extremism or violent behavior.

Defining Extremism: Why the Patriot Movement?

Every discussion concerning extremism and terrorism is incomplete without a definition for each term. For the purposes of this paper, *extremism* is defined as “political, ideological, or religious fanaticism to the point of uncompromising, unreasonable, or violent action.”²⁰ *Terrorism* takes extremism a step further, turning it into “violent acts intended to induce widespread fear to promote a cause or achieve political, ideological, or religious goals.” This paper focuses heavily on right-wing extremism and defines *right wing* as “deeply conservative, unprogressive, or reactionary politically or socially, usually for religious or racial reasons.” Despite common populist narratives, right-wing

19. See Leman and Cinnirella’s (2013) work, which shows that belief in one conspiracy theory tends to lead to an acceptance of additional conspiracy theories. Bartlett and Miller (2010) explained how conspiracism can lead to violence. See Chapter 5 for a discussion on how conspiracism can become justification for terrorism.

20. George and Wilcox (1992) pointed out that groups tend to label people with whom they disagree as “extremists” (56). This is an unfair use of the term since extremism is “more an issue of style than of content,” meaning extremists take political action beyond reasonable limits, are intolerant of opposing views, and adopt means that show disregard for the life, liberty, or rights of others (54).

extremists are typically exclusionary in the sense that they believe that certain rights, privileges, or powers should be enjoyed by some but denied to others.²¹

As Chapter 5 will discuss, conspiracism is common within extremist ideologies across the ideological spectrum. The conclusions presented in this thesis should apply to most conspiracy-theory-based forms of extremism. This paper focuses almost exclusively on right-wing extremism in the United States because of its relevance to the case study and avenue for application, i.e. the US Army. From Christian-fundamentalism-inspired groups to the Sovereign Citizens and Patriot militias, right-wing extremists in America are becoming increasingly active (Bergen and Sterman 2014; Johnson 2012; Morgenstern 2013). All of these groups, movements, and organizations fall under the blanket term *Patriot movement* and will be referred to as such,²² but, when necessary, individual groups will be identified and explained in more detail. Though Patriot groups may express differing opinions or goals, they all share common conspiracy theory-based beliefs.

Research Design: Focus and Intent

This paper does not present the Patriot movement as *de facto* extremist or terrorist. The moniker itself is bound to attract support from people who simply seek to express their patriotism. The movement includes a wide range of individuals, groups, and organizations, many of which differ drastically in how they choose to voice their opinions about political, religious, and social matters. Some are essentially peaceful while others are inherently violent. This paper focuses on groups that *do* tend toward violent forms of

21. Weinberg (2013) contrasts right-wing populist groups with right-wing “hate” groups, both of which are revolutionary, yet exclusionary for different reasons (16–17). Populist groups tend to exclude elites or political parties while hate groups exclude racial or ethnic groups.

22. *Patriots* or *Christian Patriots* may also be used as a synonym for *Patriot movement*.

extremism. It concentrates on Patriot movement groups because they are the most prominent distributors of conspiracist propaganda in the United States. They also offer one of the most popular forms of extremism in America and are the most likely to both actively and passively recruit service members.

As stated earlier, conspiracism is not a new phenomenon, and it is not unique to American culture or to the 20th Century. This paper focuses primarily on post–World War II conspiracy theories and extremist groups because they are the most relevant to modern extremism in the United States. The conspiracy theories created during the Cold War era set the stage for twenty-first century American conspiracism. They were instrumental in forming the conspiracist ideations held by both foreign and domestic extremist groups today. As Chapter 3 will demonstrate, the type of religio-political narrative used during the anti-communism movement serves as an excellent case study for the long-term effects of Manichean discourse in politics and popular culture. It also provides a framework for understanding how conspiracism can become an integral component of extremist ideologies.

Although individual conspiracies or conspiracy theories may be discussed as cases in point, it is not this paper’s intent to prove, refute, or evaluate evidence for or against any specific conspiracy theory. The focus lies not on the veracity of individual conspiracies or theories, but on conspiracism, its possible negative effects, and ways to defeat the conspiracist mentality. The conspiracy theories espoused by extremist groups do, however, serve as evidence to support their ideologies and will be used to demonstrate how they can shape extremist worldviews. Similarly, this paper does not seek to support or oppose the claims of any specific movement. It does not intend to

predict terrorist attacks, nor does it suggest counterterrorism policies or procedures. Furthermore, this paper does not present conspiracists as *de facto* violent, nor does it claim that conspiracy theories should be equated with violent extremism. Most conspiracists do not—at least openly—support extremism and, as Professor Mark Fenster, PhD (2008) points out, many engage “in conspiracy theory at some level, whether for pleasure or as a potential explanation for events in their lives” (1).²³ For some people, conspiracy theories are simply a hobby.

As will be discussed in later chapters, conspiracism can and does, however, sometimes lead to or become justification for extremist or terrorist activity. It should be taken seriously when studying extremist ideologies. This paper seeks to make that point and to contribute to the research in multiple fields of study. Chapter 3 will provide an historical case study on the spread of conspiracism through Manichean, religio-political discourse. It will also explore the effects of the conspiracism-laden ideology of the resultant Patriot movement. Chapter 4 will draw specific attention to military veteran involvement in American right-wing extremist organizations and to the tendency for such groups to recruit service members. Chapter 5 will explore possible reasons for conspiratorial beliefs and describe how conspiracism defines extremists’ worldviews, aids in recruitment, and can lead to more violent forms of extremism. Chapter 6 will suggest an education-based approach for combating conspiracism and discuss how such an approach could apply to US Army education and critical-thinking training. Chapter 7 will summarize the research contained in this thesis and offer suggestions for further

23. Oliver and Wood (2014, 953) found that over half of Americans claim to believe in one or more conspiracy theories, but the number of people who engage in extremism is obviously proportionally low. See Banas and Miller (2013), Public Policy Polling (2013), and Shermer (2014) for additional statistics about widespread belief in conspiracy theories.

research in related fields of study. I am hopeful that this analysis will add value to the current literature concerning conspiracy theories, right-wing extremism, and education-based approaches to curbing violent behavior. The goal of this project is to draw attention to an often-overlooked aspect of extremist ideologies and to better the US Army by educating the force while guarding against conspiracy-theory-based extremism within its ranks.²⁴

24. This paper does not suggest that conspiracism is the only or ultimate cause of extremism. Conspiracism is only one of many factors that can lead to extreme beliefs and behavior.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

Conspiracism in Extremism and the Patriot Movement

Much of the literature on international extremist and terrorist groups seem to address their ideologies in broad terms, such as anti-globalist or even communist. They also frequently use religious terminology, such as Jihadist or Islamist, which can cover a wide spectrum of Islam-inspired beliefs without explaining how or why specific groups get identified by such labels. *The US National Strategy for Counterterrorism* (2011), for example, sums up al-Qaeda's ideological motivations as "a distorted interpretation of Islam" offering "injustice, disorder, and destruction" in contrast to the US values of "freedom, fairness, equality, dignity, hope, and opportunity" (3, 5). "Exotic" ideologies are naturally foreign to most Americans, so authors may not be as careful to avoid broad generalizations or oversimplifications. In the literature on domestic right-wing extremism, however, such is not the case.

Many US right-wing extremist groups profess some form of Christianity, and "right-wing" can describe a number of political or social ideas. Since a large portion of Americans share a similar belief system with the groups being discussed—whether religiously, politically, or both—the vast majority of literature concerned with right-wing American extremists must, by necessity, include at least some effort to explain their motivations. Many Americans readily identify with labels such as "right-wing" or "Christian" and require somewhat detailed explanations for what distinguishes the extreme versions from more commonly held beliefs. In efforts to explain such distinctions, authors tend to highlight the role of conspiracy theories within such groups, regardless of whether or not the conspiracism aspect of their ideology is the major focus.

The Patriot movement is usually described as “anti-government.” Though this is definitely the case, most Patriots are not anti-government in the anarchical sense. They are strongly anti-federal US government with a specific focus on maintaining what they consider to be constitutionally guaranteed rights and freedom from federal oppression. While some groups advocate overthrowing or dismantling the US government, most Patriots believe that they are protecting basic American principles and are only concerned with guarding against tyranny. For the purposes of this paper, it should be understood that the term *anti-government* is used to describe all extremist groups that view the US government or its employees as their enemy, regardless of their specific beliefs or goals.

The main sources cited in this paper establish the conspiracist ideations and history of right-wing extremist groups in the United States as well as the veteran involvement within them. A host of well-known experts, such as investigative journalist Chip Berlet (1994, 2000); political scientist Leonard Weinberg, PhD (2013); former Department of Homeland Security analyst Daryl Johnson (2012); researchers John George, PhD, and Laird Wilcox (1992); and former right-wing extremist Kerry Noble (2010), have written extensive works that demonstrate the Patriot movement’s violent history and conspiracy-based ideologies. *Encyclopedia of Right-Wing Extremism In Modern American History* (2011), by historian Stephen Atkins, PhD, and *Patriots, Politics, and the Oklahoma City Bombing* (2013) by sociology professor Stuart Wright, PhD (2013), are especially comprehensive resources. Historian Kathleen Belew, PhD, concentrated specifically on veteran involvement, and—in her PhD dissertation, “Theaters of War” (2012)—she presented the Patriot movement as not only a product of the anti-communism movement, but also one of the Vietnam War. She argued that

“membership spikes in the racist right have more consistently coincided with the return of veterans from combat than with any other set of political and economic factors” (19), and she emphasized the knowledge and training veterans have supplied to extremist groups. All of the authors provide biographical accounts of key players and descriptions of the groups’ capabilities, which clearly indicate that veterans have been major players since the very beginning of the movement.

The Patriots best display their military skills, knowledge, and willingness to mobilize in their paramilitary militias. Terrorism experts Cindy Combs, PhD, Elizabeth Combs and Lydia Marsh described the militias’ skills, training, and ideology in *The Making of a Terrorist: Volume II: Recruiting, Training, and Root Causes* (2005), edited by former director of Terrorism Studies at the United States Military Academy, James J.F. Forest, PhD.²⁵ The authors rooted the militia-affiliated Patriots’ history in Christian fundamentalism and a deeply held belief in the constitutional right to bear arms.²⁶ Combs, Combs, and Marsh described veteran-led tactical and strategic training as well as Patriot doctrine, which advocates leaderless, cellular organization and stresses the use of subversion and unconventional tactics versus open warfare. Combs, Combs, and Marsh also pointed out that today’s militias demonstrate high levels of training in firearms, explosives, armory skills, and outdoor survival techniques. These types of expertise, combined with veteran experience in military tactics and war, bring dangerous capabilities to anti-government extremist groups. Additionally, recent articles and reports

25. As discussed in Chapter 3, the *Patriot militias* or *Militia movement* began in the early 1960s, but did not become popular until after the incidents at Ruby Ridge and Waco.

26. This paper defines *Christian fundamentalism* as “strict adherence to biblical teachings and principles through a belief in the infallibility of the Bible as a literal guide to morality, history, and the nature of reality.”

by journalists, think tanks, hate-group watchdog organizations, and government agencies indicate that the Patriot militias are currently highly active.

In his book *To Shake Their Guns in the Tyrant's Face* (2014), American history professor Robert H. Churchill, PhD, questioned the notion that the Patriot militias are inherently extreme. He views the Militia movement as an extension of American political history framed in libertarianism. Churchill analyzed three historical case studies of militias in US history and interviewed members of the modern movement. He found the Patriot militias to be little more than descendants of revolutionary groups, such as the Sons of Liberty, and pointed out that the majority of Patriot members are not likely to commit acts of terrorism or violence but instead wish only to protect American citizens from tyrannical government. Churchill is correct in stating that most militia members are not likely to commit violent acts, but under the right conditions—and a perception of tyranny—many could be persuaded to do so.

Several Journalists, such as Barton Gellman (2010), Leah Nelson (2012), Justine Sharrock (2010), and Gianna Toboni (2015), conducted recent interviews, training, and patrols with various Patriot groups. Nelson joined communities along the US-Mexico border in which anti-government militia groups, anti-immigration Minutemen, and Christian fundamentalist church leaders joined forces to create paramilitary congregations. The groups propagate “New World Order” conspiracy theories, advocate Bible-based theocratic government, participate in extreme pro-gun politics, train tactically, and actively patrol the border. Members with obvious military experience lead militia activities and run paramilitary training that ranges from marksmanship and general firearms skills to tactical patrolling and infantry techniques. The groups combine

religion, ideology, and tactics to create an anti-government militant movement fueled by conspiracism. They distribute recruitment aids and training propaganda, such as a DVD entitled *To Teach them War*, and host speaking events featuring popular leaders within the Patriot movement.

Gellman described a less religiously inspired but equally conspiracist group, the Ohio Defense Force—a 300-member private militia. He attended their live-fire culmination exercise, which topped off a year-long training regimen. He witnessed a sophisticated training event that included military-style raids and ambushes that incorporated blank rounds and explosives. The group’s military veterans train its members on tactics and techniques from sniper missions to close-quarters combat and knife fighting skills. In the training scenario Gellman attended, a “pro-Muslim” president has ordered a stand down against Islamic groups operating in the United States. The Ohio Defense Force fought an opposition force dressed to resemble US federal agents (1). Many of the militia members expect a similar real-world scenario to take place and are stockpiling weapons and food while preparing defensive positions in preparation for what they believe is a coming war between the federal government and the American people. The militia’s leaders are on record saying, “the day will come ... sooner than later” (1).

Sharrock found a similar attitude among former and current military service members. She identifies groups like Oath Keepers, who specifically recruit veteran and active-duty military and law enforcement personnel.²⁷ Oath Keepers uses anti-Obama, New-World-Order, and 9/11 conspiracy theories to encourage recruits to pledge an oath to rebel against the federal government in response to events they deem unconstitutional. Oath Keepers vow to turn on their commanders and other federal employees under

27. See Chapter 4 for more information on Oath Keepers.

specific conspiracy-theory-based conditions, such as upon receipt of orders to enforce gun-control laws. These types of popular “constitutional” groups include active, reserve, retired and veteran service members from privates to generals and from every branch of the armed forces.

Sharrock interviewed US Army active-duty soldiers, bringing to light a military world steeped in conspiracy and paranoia. These soldiers actively recruit other members of the armed forces while preparing for war against the federal government. They admit to caching weapons and strategizing against their perceived enemy—the very government they work for. They are convinced that the Obama administration is intent on declaring martial law, that the New World Order will intern US citizens, and that 9/11 was an inside job. Such conspiracy theories have come to define their worldviews, and they openly admit that they will turn on their fellow soldiers and commanders when the time is right. In fact, they seem to be looking forward to it.

Recent reports and academic papers reinforce the information presented by the above authors and journalists. They also indicate that the Patriot movement’s numbers are growing. In *American Patriot Movement* (2010), the Center for Judicial and Executive Security (CJES) analyzed Patriot groups by detailing their history, identifying their common trends and tactics, describing their ideology, and examining case studies within the movement. The report defined several subgroups—from white supremacist organizations to anti-income tax groups, described the movement’s rich history of violence, and demonstrated that it is still active and growing. CJES indicated that some members of the Patriot movement pose a significant threat to law enforcement and government officials.

New America Foundation’s national security policy paper, *PATCON* (2012), by J.M Berger, described the FBI’s infiltration of the Patriot Movement during the early 1990s. Berger detailed the movement’s conspiracy-theory-rich history before and after McVeigh’s Oklahoma City bombing. His case study echoed the CJES report in many ways, and he described the Patriots as veteran-heavy, armed, dangerous, and very paranoid. According to Berger, the FBI’s infiltration of the movement—and its response to Patriot threats—increased the Patriots’ paranoia. The groups became less publicly active and shifted towards underground and decentralized structures. New data from the Southern Poverty Law Center (SPLC 2010; SPLC 2012; SPLC 2015a), the FBI (2008), and the Department of Homeland Security (DHS 2009), however, indicate that the Patriot movement may be reversing its course since the number of Patriot-affiliated groups has more than doubled since 2008.²⁸

Aside from the Patriot movement’s increased activity and veteran involvement, other recent trends indicate additional causes for concern. Researchers Jamie Bartlett, MA, and Carl Miller, MA, published a policy paper called *The Power of Unreason* (2010) for the British think-tank Demos. They analyzed the literature, ideology, and propaganda of over 50 extremist groups from around the globe and found “conspiracy theories are widely prevalent across [the] extremist spectrum, despite the vast differences in the extremist ideologies” (3). Not only is conspiracism common, but individual conspiracy theories also overlap amongst groups, creating the potential for collaboration and expanded recruiting pools (4, 5). Bartlett and Miller identified the anti-globalist

28. Journalist Madeleine Morgenstern (2013) reported an increase from 149 groups in 2008 to 1,360 in 2012. The figures come from Southern Poverty Law Center (SPLC) and some scholars question the SPLC’s methods for determining which groups make the list. Although the specific numbers may differ, most sources agree that Patriot-affiliated groups have more than doubled since 2008.

belief that Jewish elites secretly control the world's major governments as the most commonly believed conspiracy theory among extremist groups, a view shared by the Patriot movement and Islamist-Jihadist organizations around the world (21).

Paul Brister and Nina Kollars—both PhD candidates at the time of publication—addressed the possibility of group collaborations and assessed the Patriot movement's potential to use Weapons of Mass Destruction (WMD) in their article, "Pass Em' Right" (2011).²⁹ They focused primarily on the Patriots' intent and capabilities to determine the likelihood of a right-wing extremist WMD attack within the United States. Brister and Kollars analyzed anti-government, conspiracy theory-based propaganda to present an ideological basis for right-wing domestic terrorist attacks. They also provided a detailed conspiracy theory-laced history of the movement from the late 1950s to the present that—when combined with weapons stockpiling, intense training, and past attempts at chemical attacks—supports Brister and Kollars' conclusion that some members within the movement do intend to acquire and use WMDs.³⁰

As the literature suggests, at least some members of the Patriot movement pose a substantial risk to US security. Chapter 3 will elaborate on more specific historical accounts of domestic terrorism and right-wing extremism in the United States. It will also highlight the power of conspiracism-based ideology to drive some Americans to commit acts of extreme violence within their home country. As Chapter 4 will show, veterans have historically filled some of the most extreme positions within the Patriot movement,

29. Brister and Kollars (2011) defined WMD as "any chemical, biological, radiological or nuclear device employed with the purpose to inflict harm upon either humans or physical structures" without regard to the actual effects of the device (51). To date, extremist attempts to use WMDs have yielded low casualty rates, so Brister and Kollars focused their analysis of WMD capability on the physical characteristics of the device, not the potential outcome of its use.

30. Although Brister and Kollars determined that some Patriots intend to acquire and use WMDs, they found the chance of an imminent attack to be low due to the Patriots' lack of capability (63).

and they seem to be moving toward the forefront of its modern groups. Although the literature fails to present a compelling case for major concern over imminent WMD attacks or Christian-Islamic terrorist collaborations, it does bring attention to the Patriot movement's capabilities, popular support, and willingness to commit violence.

Conspiracy Theory and the Conspiracist Mentality

Only recently has the world of academia begun to seriously study the causes and effects of conspiracism. In 1964, Pulitzer Prize-winning historian Richard Hofstadter, PhD, published a seminal essay on conspiracy theories called "The Paranoid Style in American Politics." Inspired by right-wing political and extremist movements at the time, Hofstadter sought to describe the role of conspiracy theory in American culture. His essay traced the roots of modern conspiracism to fears of an Illuminati or Masonic plot to destroy religious establishments and overturn governments (78–79),³¹ which he correlated to the anti-communism movement of the Cold War. Hofstadter presented conspiracism as the result of a somewhat delusional paranoia fueled by "certain religious traditions, certain social structures and national inheritances, certain historical catastrophes or frustrations [that] may be conducive to the release of such psychic energies" (86). As Jeffery Sheldon pointed out in his Master's thesis, "Paranoid Politics" (2009), Hofstadter's essay identified the tendency for American politicians to utilize fear as a tool to sway public opinion; "the paranoid style requires a conspiracy to establish the roles everyone is expected to play, with people falling into one of two categories: 'us,' or 'them'" (4).

31. Hofstadter (1964) described the "Illuminism" movement of the 18th century as a "somewhat naïve and utopian movement" that "aspired ultimately to bring the human race under the rules of reason" (78).

Hofstadter's work became foundational to modern scholarship, but more current theories largely discount delusion or paranoia as prerequisites for conspiracist ideation. Scholars disagree on the root cause of conspiracism. Since most causes have more than one root, various approaches to a theory of conspiracy theory describe multiple aspects of a complex phenomenon. Scholars from the fields of political science, psychology, and philosophy are the major contributors to conspiracism studies,³² but even seemingly unrelated subjects, such as evolutionary biology and neuroscience, offer unique perspectives. Recognizing that no single discipline alone explains human dynamics or decision-making, most scholars readily intertwine aspects from multiple fields into their work. They tend to disagree, however, on the typical profile of a conspiracist. Though Hofstadter equated conspiracism with paranoia, psychologists Marius Raab et al. (2013), describe it as “common, regulative and possibly benign” (1), and Professor Mark Fenster, PhD (2008), found it to be “an integral aspect of American and perhaps modern and postmodern life” (9). For Fenster, conspiracy theories are largely the result of “the longstanding populist strain in American political culture” (9), which is better understood through the lens of “political strategies, not pathologies” (10).

Political scientists Eric J. Oliver, PhD, and Thomas J. Wood confirmed the American propensity for political conspiracism in “Conspiracy Theories and the Paranoid Style(s) of Mass Opinion” (2014). They conducted a research study on conspiracy

32. For psychology works see Brotherton (2013), Franks, Bangerter, and Bauer (2013), Goertzel (1994, 2011), Jolley (2013), Lantian (2013), Leman and Cinnirella (2013), Novella (2013), Raab et al. (2013), Swami et al. (2011), Thresher-Andrews (2013), and Wood (2013). For philosophy (epistemology) see Basham (2001), Dentith (2012, 2014), Mandik (2007), Pigden (2007), and Rääkkä (2009). For sociology and political work see Barkun (2003), Bennett (2007), Cimino (2005), Fenster (2008), Kravitz (1999), Oliver and Wood (2014), Sunstein and Vermeule (2009), Uscinski, Parent, and Torres (2011), and White (2001). For additional work see Aaronovitch (2010), Banas and Miller (2013), Bartlett and Miller (2010), Coughlin (1999), Goldberg (2001), Hodapp and Von Kannon (2008), Hofstadter (1964), and Melley (2002).

theories for the University of Chicago that demonstrated that religious people (especially those who believe in “end times”), the socially disempowered, and people with Manichean worldviews, tend to be most susceptible to belief in conspiracy theories (961).³³ According to their analysis, “over half of the American population consistently endorse[s] some kind of conspiratorial narrative about a current political event or phenomenon” (953). The tendency to “interpret history relative to universal struggles between good and evil” is “common in both religious and populist rhetoric” (954), especially in the United States, where Americans demonstrate high familiarity and agreement with conspiracy theories (956).

In “Constructing an American Fear Culture from Red Scares to Terrorism” (2013), socio-cultural anthropologist Geoffrey Skoll, PhD, and economist Maximiliano Korstanje, PhD, explored the role of fear in American culture. They described the current US “obsession with terrorism” as an “outgrowth of anti-communist hysterias” and a modern manifestation of the Cold War Red Scare (341). Skoll and Korstanje’s work on fear cultures provides a solid foundation for the establishment of post–World War II conspiracism within the United States. Other authors, such as historian Robert Alan Goldberg, PhD (2001); Professor Jonathan White, PhD (2001); Professor Bennett Kravitz, PhD (1999); Professor Timothy Melley, PhD (2002); and Professor Michael Barkun, PhD (2003), present additional evidence for religious and fear-based drives toward conspiracism in American society. Additionally, the religio-political discourse used during the Cold War era provides valuable insight into the anti-communism movement and the Manichean ideology that accompanied it. Documentaries, primary

33. “End times” describes an eschatological belief in the “end of history from a religious perspective” (Robinson 2013). Oliver and Wood’s (2014) study refers specifically to belief in Biblical end-times prophecy (959), although other religious traditions contain similar beliefs (Rohmann 1999, 120–21).

sources, and the extensive work of historian Dianne Kirby, PhD (2013); Professor Markku Ruotsila, PhD (2012, 2103); historian Andrew Preston, PhD (2012); historian Jay Learned, PhD (2012); historian Randall Balmer, PhD (2011); Professor Thomas Aiello, PhD (2005); pastor Lee Canipe, PhD (2003); historian Ellen Schrecker, PhD (1988, 1998, 2004); historian John Lewis Gaddis, PhD (1997, 2007); and Matthew Cloud (2004) offer an historical backdrop for the role religion played in the politics of anti-communism in the United States from the 1920s to the 1960s.

Since the anti-communism and civil-rights movements of the Cold War, the most common conspiracy theories—especially the ones propagated by the Patriot movement—relate to beliefs about the US federal government, global institutions like the United Nations (UN), and perceptions of “ruling elites.” In *Conspiracy Theories and Secret Societies for Dummies* (2008), Christopher Hodapp and Alice Von Kannon quite thoroughly described the most commonly believed conspiracy theories. They also covered the role of secret societies, such as the Freemasons, Bavarian Illuminati, and what they call “secret societies of terror and death” (219), which include The Knights of the Ku Klux Klan. In *Secrets, Plots, & Hidden Agendas* (1999), author Paul T. Coughlin (1999) provided similar information from a Christianity-specific perspective, i.e. the tendency for church congregations to spread conspiracism. Coughlin situated his analysis in eschatology, focusing on the “end times” aspect of conspiracy theories, which he related to the Christian belief in biblical prophecy. He addressed the religious and conspiratorial beliefs commonly found within the Patriot movement and described how the two ideologies play off of and reinforce each other. Coughlin explained that anti-globalism, anti-American, anti-Semitic, anti-government, and other types of conspiracy

theories intermingle and mesh with religious and apocalyptic beliefs to scare people into more extreme positions.

In “Conspiracy Theories as a Quasi-religious Mentality” (2013), psychology Professors Bradley Franks, PhD, Adrian Bangerter, PhD, and Martin Bauer, PhD, found conspiracy theories themselves to be “quasi-religious representations” that mimic institutionalized religions (2). The authors suggest that conspiracism draws on similar “resources employed” by religions and “merge the intuitive and the counterintuitive response to challenging secular events” (4). Raab et al. (2013) expanded on conspiracy theory as a type of religious or mythical story and described conspiracy theories as “narrations that help people to recognize themselves” (7). In other words, conspiracy theories can provide people with a sense of purpose in much the same way that religions do.

The human propensity toward superstitious or religious belief and the need for purpose are definitely prominent factors, but the psychology of conspiracism is a complex phenomenon. At the basic level, evolutionary biology is, of course, fundamental to how humans think. This paper draws on multiple sources in biology and neuroscience to form a basis for understanding how the human brain perceives the world around it. The bulk of the theoretical work pertaining to the evolutionary aspect of human psychology presented here comes from the relevant works of renowned biologist Edward O. Wilson, PhD (2012, 2014); somewhat notorious evolutionary biologist, Richard Dawkins, PhD (2006, 2008); cognitive scientist and philosopher Daniel Dennett, PhD (1997, 2002); evolutionary biologist David Sloan Wilson, PhD (2003); professor of biological and neurological sciences Robert Sapolsky, PhD (2010a, 2010b, 2014); neurologist Steven

Novella, MD (2013); author Daniel Gardner (2008); and futurist Ray Kurzweil, PhD (2012, 2014).

Evolutionary theory and neuroscience may explain how and why the human brain is structured the way it is, but they do not necessarily provide complete explanations for conspiracism. A number of scholars, however, have addressed human psychology with a specific focus on conspiracy theories. Sociologist Ted Goertzel, PhD (2011), borrowed ideas from some of the authors above to describe conspiracism in memetic terms.³⁴ He also suggested that conspiracist ideation is a product of alienated thinking (Goertzel 1994, 739). In “Conspiracy Theories are for Losers” (2011), however, political science Professor Joseph E. Uscinski, PhD, Professor Joseph M. Parent, PhD, and undergraduate Bethany Torres offered the following explanation:

The causes of conspiracy theories are not primarily philosophical, psychological, or sociological—they are political. Conspiracy theories tend to resonate when they help vulnerable groups manage threats. They do this because successful conspiracy theories have a strategic logic that sharpens internal cohesion and focuses attention on dangers. (5)

Uscinski, Parent, and Torres “contend that causes of conspiracy theorizing are first and foremost political,” with the other causes acting as “important intervening variables” (14). They argued that scholars in various fields tend to view the “ultimate causes” of conspiracism through the lens of their particular fields of study. Uscinski, Parent, and Torres found that conspiracy-based beliefs are common among both the local masses and the local elites (17). Though the authors fully recognize the importance of “intervening variables,” their conclusions seem to suggest that a feeling of political

34. Richard Dawkins coined the term *meme* in *The Selfish Gene* (2006), which was first published in 1976. Dawkins described the meme as a unit of human culture, much like the gene is a unit of biology. Memes, i.e. beliefs and ideas, self-replicate and spread by adopting strategies for competition and cooperation in the same evolutionary manner that life competes and cooperates for survival (Chapter 11).

disenfranchisement is usually the main drive for conspiracist ideation. Similarly, Psychologist Viren Swami, PhD (2011), and his colleagues reported that belief in conspiracy theories correlates to political cynicism, disenfranchisement, low self-esteem, and feelings of powerlessness (444, 453).

While scholars agree that a lack of political power is a major contributing factor to conspiracist ideation, other reasons seem equally significant. Professor of psychology Patrick J. Leman, PhD, and social psychologist Marco Cinnirella, PhD (2013), conducted a study that demonstrated a correlation between the need for cognitive closure (NFCC) and the tendency to accept conspiracy theories. In other words, people with a vested interest in the story are more likely to accept faulty arguments. Leman and Cinnirella also pointed out the significance of perceptions of powerlessness, alienation, and anomie to conspiracist ideation (1).³⁵ Researchers Christopher Thresher-Andrews, Robert Brotherton, Anthony Lantian, Michael Wood, and Daniel Jolley expanded on the aforementioned psychological contributors to conspiracism in a special issue of *Psychology Postgraduate Affairs Group Quarterly* (2013). They also operate a website dedicated to the psychology of conspiracy theories, *conspiracypsychology.com*, which offers a wealth of information on the subject.

Psychology and philosophy seem to go hand-in-hand, especially in regards to conspiracism. When people desperate for cognitive closure lack the knowledge they need to reach it, they sometimes suffer a type of epistemological crisis.³⁶ The idea that such a

35. Anomie refers to a faulty relationship between individuals and societies in which the society at large fails to provide overarching moral guidance to individuals and groups. Anomic situations reflect a breakdown of social norms and values.

36. Epistemology is the philosophical study of the theory of knowledge. It essentially asks questions about how humans know what they do and what distinguishes justified knowledge from opinion.

situation leads to conspiracism is central to the conclusions presented in this thesis. In “Conspiracy Theories: Causes and Cures” (2009), Professors of Law Cass R. Sunstein, PhD, and Adrian Vermeule, PhD, claimed that conspiracy theories are the result of a “‘crippled epistemology’ in the form of a sharply limited number of (relevant) informational sources” (204). Sunstein and Vermeule further explained that human minds “protest against chaos” (208). When people do not possess enough relevant information to understand the meaning behind certain events or situations, conspiracy theories tend to supply the answers they need. According to philosopher Lee Basham, PhD (2001), conspiracy theories offer “an important epistemic virtue [with] unparalleled explanatory completeness” (268).

If conspiracism results from knowledge gaps and superstition, then education could be the key to solving conspiracy-based epistemological crises. Renowned author and skeptic Michael Shermer linked education to conspiracism in “Why do People Believe in Conspiracy Theories?” (2014). Shermer explained that “education makes a difference in reducing conspiratorial thinking.” He referenced some of Uscinski and Parent’s newest research, which reported that 42% of Americans without high school diplomas show high conspiratorial predispositions. Furthermore, higher degrees negatively correlate to such beliefs. As Shermer pointed out, however, 23% of Americans with postgraduate degrees still maintain a high predisposition to belief in conspiracy theories. That is a high enough percentage to suggest that education alone may not be enough to defeat conspiracism; however, Professor John Banas, PhD, and Gregory Miller (2013) offered another promising solution. Banas and Miller were able to lessen the effectiveness of conspiracy theory propaganda on college students by providing

inoculation messages prior to exposure.³⁷ Their research suggests that targeted education under the right conditions may be an effective weapon against conspiracist ideation or belief.

Army Education and Critical Thinking

As discussed in Chapter 6, this paper suggests an education-based approach for combating the conspiracism that can lead to extremism. As an avenue for application, it focuses on the US Army's Professional Military Education (PME) system and critical-thinking training. It is beyond the scope of this research to address military education in general— as each of its branches employ different education strategies—but because of the author's personal experience, vested interest, and access to the knowledge of peers, the Army is an opportune resource and venue for theory application.

Due to the time constraints for researching this thesis, an in-depth analysis of Army training and education was not possible; however, the sources used in this research are sufficient to demonstrate the Army's current approach. Much of the relevant documents used are publicly available, but some of the information comes from lesson plans for Army professional development courses. To maintain course integrity, these documents are controlled items and are not made available to unauthorized persons. They will not be directly cited and nothing in this paper will compromise any course's instruction process.

This research includes input from a pool of over 50 senior noncommissioned officers and junior to field-grade commissioned officers, all of whom possess extensive

37. Banas and Miller (2013) used fact and logic-based inoculation messages before exposing students to an excerpt from *Loose Change: Final Cut* (2007), which proposes that the 9/11 attacks were an inside job. The students who received inoculation messages demonstrated higher resistance to the video's message than those in the control group.

experience in the Special Operations community. In addition, the author has nearly 12 years of military service and over two years of personal experience as an instructor in the Warrior, Advanced, and Senior Leader courses for noncommissioned officers. As a result, first-hand experience largely influences the suggestions offered in Chapters 6 and 7. If this research fails to reflect the Army's current goals for critical-thinking or professional development training, then those goals are not being properly expressed at the instructor or student levels.

This thesis' conclusions support *The U.S. Army Learning Concept for 2015* (DA 2011), which describes "how the Army will train and educate Soldiers and leaders in individual knowledge, skills, attributes, and abilities to execute full-spectrum operations" (1). The new Army Learning Concept (ALC) focuses on adapting Army instruction to incorporate learner-centric teaching using experiential-learning methodology. ALC also employs adult-learning models, which recognize the differences between pedagogy and andragogy to tailor teaching towards adult learners (14, 19).³⁸ Finally, ALC seeks to develop "an adaptive, career-long individual learning model" that most instructors refer to as "life-long learning" (5).

Along with integrating new learning models to better educate students, the Army also actively seeks to develop critically thinking leaders. To better understand the Army's approach to critical thinking in regard to leadership and operations, this paper references Army Doctrine Publication (ADP) 2-0, *Intelligence* (DA 2012a); ADP 5-0, *The*

38. Pedagogy and Andragogy describe two types of teaching methods. Pedagogical teaching is instructor-centric in the sense that the student depends almost entirely on the teacher for information. People who teach children typically use pedagogical methods. Andragogy, on the other hand, focuses on the principles of adult learning in which the student takes a more active role in the leaning process. For more information on adult learning, see "Adult Learning Theory and Principles" at <http://www.qotfc.edu.au/resource/?page=65375> (Accessed April 2, 2015).

Operations Process (DA 2012b); ADP 6-0, *Mission Command* (DA 2014a); the Center for Army Leadership's *Leader Development Improvement Guide* (CAL 2012); and the *Army Leader Development Strategy* (DA 2013). Additionally, research focused specifically on enhancing Army critical-thinking training by the US Army Research Institute (Cohen, Salas, and Riedel 2002; Fischer, Spiker, and Riedel 2008, 2009a, 2009b), the RAND Corporation (Straus et al. 2013), and Colonel (Retired) Stephen Gerras, PhD (2008), provide valuable insights into teaching critical thinking in terms of Army leadership.

Aside from Army-specific sources, this paper suggests approaches to critical-thinking training based on research from scholars mentioned throughout this literature review. It also references sources specifically designed to teach critical thinking, logic, and reasoning skills, such as *Asking the Right Questions* (Browne and Keeley 2015) and *The Thinker's Guide* series by the Foundation for Critical Thinking (Elder and Paul 2008a, 2008b, 2009, 2010). Understanding and employing different types of critical thinking is fundamental to this paper's thesis, as the traditional "think outside of the box" approach may not be enough to defeat conspiracism. Additionally, this research references Army Regulation (AR) 381-12, *Threat Awareness and Reporting Program* (DA 2010), which is the Army's guide "to ensure that DA [Department of the Army] personnel recognize and report incidents and indicators of attempted or actual espionage, subversion, terrorism or extremist activities" (1).

CHAPTER 3: THE CONSPIRACIST STYLE IN AMERICAN EXTREMISM

As a study that concerns both religion and politics—both of which can be controversial in various ways—this chapter must include a disclaimer. This is not an exposition on the separation of Church and State. That separation exists for a variety of reasons and is meant to protect both the Church and the State from each another.³⁹ The focus here is not on the use of religious discourse in politics *per se*. That is another discussion entirely. This study explores the *type* of religio-political discourse—specifically, Manichean—that pervaded American society during the early Cold War.

In the 3rd century C.E., a Persian religious movement called Manichaeism taught that creation itself is the reflection of a cosmic struggle between opposing forces of good and evil. Its followers defined reality in terms of a good, spiritual world and an evil, material world. The two forces constantly clashed in a struggle for supremacy.⁴⁰ Today’s modern derivative, *Manichean*, defines a similar philosophy. People with a Manichean perspective describe world events as matters of good versus evil. From a Manichean point of view, political and social events are consequences of interactions of “good people and malevolent people, rather than between self-interested actors ... of different perspectives and priorities” (Oliver and Wood 2014, 953).

In the early days of the Cold War, Western—“Christian”—democracy and Soviet—“atheistic”—communism became locked in a Manichean struggle. With deep roots in religious fundamentalism, patriotism, and anti-communism, the Patriot

39. For more on Church-State separation in the Western tradition, see James (1927), Knowles (1967), Deane (1973), Gould (1997), and Witte (2006). Witte’s “Facts and Fiction About the History of Separation of Church and State” discusses the “five understandings ... in the founding era” (28–30).

40. See “Manichaeism” (2015), and Rohmann (1999, 108–09).

movement emerged as a self-proclaimed protector of the American way of life. Although economic, political, and social pressures played large roles—and similar groups existed prior to World War II—the frequent mixture of religious, patriotic, and fear-based discourse was instrumental in shaping the conspiracist ideation that fueled anti-government extremism. Patriot leaders fused anti-communist, anti-government, and anti-globalist rhetoric with religious and patriotic themes to create fear-based conspiracy theories that still continue to evolve and flourish. The Manichean perspective became fundamental to anti-communist conspiracism. For many people, it would come to define their patriotism.

The religio-political, Manichean discourse of the Cold War profoundly affected American culture. Its effects are still felt today. Of course, religion was only one part of a much larger multi-causal story, but it played a significant role. America and its allies faced very real physical threats, many of which wholly justified healthy fear and uncertainty. The United States entered the Second World War for a host of reasons, and post-war economic, geostrategic, and political realities formed a complex web of challenges for all parties involved. No one had many options. After the war, Communists posed real dangers to human rights, and they actually did conduct extensive spying, espionage, and propaganda operations—but so did the United States.⁴¹ Historian John Lewis Gaddis, PhD (1997, 25), explained that Stalin had launched cold wars throughout his life. He waged them against his own family, his comrades, foreign Communists, and veterans of the Red Army. He had “transformed his country into an extension of himself,” and “suspicion, distrust, and an abiding cynicism were not only his preferred but his necessary environment; he could not function apart from it.” The West’s use of

41. See *Biography* (1996), Gaddis (1997, 6), Nye and Welch (2013, 155), and Heale (1996).

religious ideology to combat the Soviets, however, created a type of conflict that “precluded compromise” (Kirby 2013, 27:30–32:47). As historian Dianne Kirby, PhD (2013), argued, “one can explain the Cold War perfectly well ... without reference to religion because it was a power struggle ... but religion brings in another element ... that gives us a deeper and more nuanced understanding” (55:00–55:31). According to Professor Vessela Misheva, PhD (2006), the Cold War was a “war of minds” (300). Both sides described the other in Manichean terms. Each had “their own ‘Big Brothers’ to watch over all interactions,” and “both systems could be said to have had their own forms of ‘McCarthyism’” (301). The American version relied heavily on religion, and the good-versus-evil narrative became fundamental to Patriot ideology.

The Birth of a Christian Nation

The hideous face of atheistic world communism at long last is unveiled for all who have eyes to see. It is the most monstrous mass of organized evil that history has known. It is the sum of all villainies. — Frederick Brown Harris, Senate Chaplain (quoted in Peacock 2014, 70)

The Scopes Trial of 1925, which publicized teaching the theory of evolution in public schools, catalyzed a Christian-fundamentalist movement across the United States (Lambert 2010; Linder 2014). Threatened by new ideas that they believed might challenge people’s faith, Christian-fundamentalist pastors and organizations saturated the American public with fundamentalist messages in print and radio (Ruotsila 2012, 381). Christian organizations planned to evangelize the masses through Youth for Christ programs, which took hold nationwide by the early 1940s (Haraldsson 2011). Although war machines were ravaging Europe, Christian fundamentalists concentrated their efforts against scientific modernity at home (Glazer, Lewis, and Tanenhaus 2004, 26–27). Theirs

was a war to maintain the moral high ground—and one to save souls—but their spiritual war would quickly become corporeal.

Facing predominantly isolationist attitudes, US politicians began employing increasingly Manichean-type dialogue to create a religiously flavored narrative for the war in Europe. President Franklin Delano Roosevelt (FDR)—a devout Protestant—became the first American president to involve the Vatican in diplomacy by treating it as a sovereign state (Preston 2012, 342). In 1940, he assigned a personal representative to the Vatican in an attempt to unify the United States with millions of Europeans against communism (343).⁴² After Italy declared war on Britain and France, however, Nazism became the new enemy of religion and was touted as a promoter of atheism, paganism, and idolatry of the State.

Once Germany turned on its Soviet ally, America sided with the lesser of two evils. Despite the new Soviet-American alliance, many Christian anti-communists, denounced the partnership, and firmly labeled communism as the “totalitarian enemies of Christian democracy” (363). As Kirby (2013) explained, the West generalized communist views regarding religion, but Stalin did, in fact, allow a degree of religious freedom within the Soviet Union. According to Christian absolutists, however, communism embodied supreme evil and was inherently bent on world domination (12:40–17:53).⁴³

42. Roosevelt did not assign an official ambassador and did not create a true diplomatic relationship with the Vatican due to political concerns. By appointing a US representative he sparked “a wave of Protestant anger” over church/state separation and concerns of undue Catholic influence in US government (Preston 2012, 344).

43. Kirby (2013) explained that the Soviets were not necessarily anti-religious but instead simply non-religious. Stalin did not oppose religion because of religious belief *per se*. He persecuted all opposition, including any with a religious flavor. The Soviets tolerated religion when it suited their needs as demonstrated by the fact that they rallied religious support to defeat the Nazis (9:55–18:00).

While anti-communists concentrated on an ideological struggle in America, Britain faced a more menacing foe. Still a “devoted churchgoing nation” (Preston 2012, 347), Britons filled churches seeking solace and spiritual comfort from the rapidly decaying world around them. British Prime Minister Winston Churchill capitalized on the power of religious unification by contrasting Christianity with Nazism. He framed “Britain’s struggle with evil in explicitly Christian terms” (347), and he hoped to garner American support by exclaiming:

It is no exaggeration to say that the future of the whole world, and the hopes of a broadening civilization founded upon Christian ethics, depend upon the relations between the British empire, or commonwealth of nations, and the United States of America. (Rue 1941)

His words resonated throughout the American religious community and helped spark a new wave of Manichean calls to action.

Although much of America remained largely isolationist or pacifist (Preston 2012, 348), many religious and political leaders quickly adjusted their strong, anti-war stance to one in favor of peace by military victory (368). Religious leaders became public intellectuals, reaching millions of Americans through radio, newspapers, and magazines. They echoed expressions similar to Churchill’s description of the war, shaping it in terms of good Christian democracy versus evil Nazi fascism (351–69). Christian realists transformed pre–World War I Christian pacifism into Christian military interventionism (297–314), and major political figures, such as Vice President Henry Wallace, called democracy “the one true political expression of Christianity” (366). Roosevelt commandeered church services as symbols of solidarity (350), and many Americans began to view the war in Europe as a Manichean struggle against evil forces set out to destroy Christian democracy.

After the Japanese attacked Pearl Harbor, Christian leaders quickly “uncovered Japan’s supposed plot against religious freedom.” They began calling the Japanese “un-Christian” and US diplomats in Asia emphasized reports of Japanese cruelty toward Christian missionaries (368). The majority of Christians and Jews in America came to support what they viewed as a religious war for freedom against the evils of fascism, paganism, and atheism (367). Wartime leaders built support for the war by using the “rhetoric of faith” to—quite literally—demonize the enemy (366). The US military began distributing morality propaganda to its troops, as soldiers became crusaders for righteous nationalism (367–72).⁴⁴ Meanwhile, FDR’s “fireside chats” encouraged US citizens to pray continuously. He asked for prayers for strength against tyrannical enemies who would enslave mankind, calling Nazism and fascism “unholy forces of our enemy” (366). Political and religious leaders had created a holy war against the forces of evil and loosed an anti-religion bogeyman upon American society before sending it to war.

With the allies victorious, isolationist attitudes once again dominated American popular opinion (Kirby 2013), but FDR’s wartime rhetoric of “good” versus “evil” had sparked a strong religious reaction (Learned 2012, 94). Before the war, American Christians had nearly unanimously opposed communism (Preston 2012, 353), and the Vatican had declared it an “unspeakable doctrine” that would destroy human society (355). With the Nazis defeated, many Christians returned to the more familiar struggle.

As Jay Learned explained in his PhD dissertation (2012):

Evangelical Christians, who considered themselves the guardian of Manichean ideology during the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, played the crucial role of Vanguard of revived messianism in postwar America. ... Their understanding that Soviet messianism intended to recreate the world in the Soviet image provided the dire animus required

44. Religious leaders called anyone opposed to the war “unpatriotic” (Preston 2012, 367–72).

to mobilize evangelicals and the nation. Well ahead of the American public, they demonized the Marxist foe and mobilized for spiritual warfare against it. (94)

Understandably, the war had brought with it a true sense of urgency, which the allied victory did not fully relieve. Europe became a battleground for spiritual warfare, and Christian missionaries flooded the continent during its reconstruction. For many people of a religious faith, communism represented everything that their religion did not.

Like the anti-communist missionaries, President Harry S. Truman had entered the Cold War using religion as a not-so-secret weapon against Soviet expansion (Kirby 2013; Preston 2012, 411–12). He followed FDR’s lead by employing religious rhetoric to unite the nation against isolationism. He declared a national day of prayer to thank God for victory, asking him to guide America into a path of peace (373). Truman also expanded US-Vatican relations by publicly corresponding with Pope Pius XII. In a letter to the Pope, Truman explained his “heartfelt conviction that those who do not recognize their responsibility to Almighty God cannot meet their full duty toward their fellow men.” He firmly labeled America a “Christian nation,” reinforcing the wartime melding of Christianity with patriotism. He stated that an “enduring peace can be built only upon Christian principles,” and “ask[ed] each to do his part by renewing devotion to religion” (Balmer 2011, 43; Truman 1947). Although the hot war had ended, a cold war between the Christian nation and the “godless Soviet bogey” had just begun (Kirby 2013, 32:42).

The Truman administration generalized communist views about religion, oversimplified Soviet intentions, and supported Christian absolutist perceptions that communism was inherently anti-religion, the embodiment of pure evil, and determined to dominate the world (Kirby 2013, 17:00–18:00). Truman prepared for the war between

rival ideologies and planned to unite the world's religions against the atheistic communist threat (Preston 2012, 414, 417). Anti-communism became a rhetorical device for the West's unification of shared interests, ethics, and morality. As journalists reported anti-state propaganda as religious persecution, the Manichean narrative justified military expansion (Kirby 2013, 17:50–32:00).

While Truman employed Christianity as justification for policies, Christian fundamentalists extended their wartime mobilization to bring religious conviction to all aspects of American life (Preston 2012, 382). As historian Andrew Preston, PhD (2012), explained, “World War II marked a decisive shift in religious attitudes toward patriotism” (371). It rescued fundamentalists from their reputations for political and theological extremism, and they turned their attack toward America's morality. Through uncompromising patriotism, they employed their newfound political power to initiate a crusade for religion and democracy (371–73). Christian fundamentalists saturated American culture with religious propaganda and implored their followers to lobby for political action against communist influence (Ruotsila 2012, 391–98). As post-war revivals broke out across the United States, Youth for Christ's anti-communist missionaries headed overseas. Their first ministerial team in Europe included the soon-to-be-famous evangelical, Billy Graham, who would return to the United States and launch a nationwide revival, spreading his message of love for God and country—plus the evils of communism (Learned 2012, 45–119). Church attendance soared to record numbers and “by 1949, only ten percent of Americans polled believed that one could be both a communist *and* a Christian” (Balmer 2011, 43; emphasis added; PBS 2010). With religious enthusiasm sweeping the nation, Christianity and communism became

“diametrically opposed.”⁴⁵ US fears of communist expansion helped birth a new American Christian mythos—and the spiritually infused rhetoric of the late 1940s would quickly turn into mass hysteria.

When President Truman announced the first successful Soviet nuclear detonation on September 23, 1949, American fears skyrocketed. For many, the resistance to atomic control confirmed their suspicions of Soviet ill intent (PBS 2010).⁴⁶ Amidst rumors of pending nuclear annihilation, Billy Graham’s fire-and-brimstone, anti-communist message launched him to pop-star-like status. In a personality cult akin to the Beatlemania of the 1960s, Graham became a sensation (Lambert 2010). His message solidified the communist “other” as a bogeyman determined to destroy the American way of life. He preached Christian salvation as the nation’s only hope for survival and used current events to shock his audience into a sense of urgency (Learned 2012, 118). For Graham, “Christian salvation was the only vaccine against Communism” (Aiello 2005), and the “greatest and most effective weapon” against the communist threat was to be “a born again Christian” (Graham 1954, 42 quoted in Aiello 2005). Graham pioneered the use of antichrists and Armageddon on national broadcasts and linked the apocalyptic ideas directly to communism (Learned 2012, 108). His message, which reached millions, claimed that the Bible was America’s only hope against the satanic, communist regimes (Aiello 2005). According to Graham, it was “America’s obligation to smite the Soviets” (Learned 2012, 109).

45. A *New York Times* article from 1950 quotes a minister who called Christianity “diametrically opposed” to communism. He claimed that “a Christianity that was not ‘laissez-faire’ was “the only sensible alternative to communism,” adding that it “must be that of ‘an aggressive, progressive, objective Christianity’” (“Christianity Seen in War of Ideals” 1950).

46. Newspaper headlines overflowed with stories of the Soviet refusal to cooperate with atomic regulations (Friendly 1949; “Graham Hits Soviet Stand on A-Control” 1949; James 1949).

As the Manichean narrative permeated American society, terms like “terror,” “evil,” “enemy,” and “diabolical” became common descriptors for communism. Americans understood it as a force set to destroy the Church, to enslave the people, and to take over America.⁴⁷ Christianity became a prerequisite for patriotic citizenship and organizations like the Christian Anti-Communist Crusade and the National Association for Evangelicals (boasting ten million members in 1950) intertwined American patriotism with Christian beliefs (Aiello 2005). Americans began pointing fingers at each other as rumors of communist infiltrators ran amok.⁴⁸ Truman opened the “spiritual rearmament” campaign of Religion in American Life (RIAL) with a live address to the nation in which he stressed the importance of America’s “religious heritage” (Balmer 2011, 43). Celebrity endorsers for RIAL stressed the importance of religion while Graham’s messages equated “true patriotism” with loyal Christianity (Haraldsson 2011). The State Department offered Bibles and religious periodicals in information centers worldwide (Balmer 2011, 43), Americans fought over religious expression in public schools (PBS 2010), and US military leaders brought evangelism to American soldiers.⁴⁹ As pastor Lee Canipe, PhD explained (2003, 311), from the newfound American spiritual identity and “a national sense of anxiety emerged a powerful cult of conformity. In Cold War America, to be different was to be dangerous.”

47. See Arne (1952), Parrino (1954), “Red Atheism Worst Foe of Church” (1950), “Text of Bishop’s Speech Assailing McCarthy” (1954), and “The Long Arm of Communism” (1951).

48. See *Cold War* (1998), “Witness Says He Saw Bridges at Communist Party Session” (1950).

49. Brigadier General John Devine commanded recruits at Fort Knox to attend religious services, and the Air Force shuttled members of the Moody Institute of Science to evangelize the force and refute the theory of evolution (Balmer 2011, 43).

American leaders presented communism as a spreading disease. According to the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) director, J. Edgar Hoover:

Communism in reality is *not* a political party; it is a way of life—an evil and malignant way of life. It reveals a condition akin to a disease that spreads like an epidemic, and like an epidemic, a quarantine is necessary to keep it from infecting this nation. (*Cold War* 1998, 0:44–1:02)

Publicized witch-hunts for communist infiltrators became the norm. The House Un-American Activities Committee (HUAC) held hearings to stifle communist sympathizing or, worse, membership in the Communist Party, and hundreds of people ended up blacklisted from employment or behind bars for invoking their right against self-incrimination. Employee loyalty programs denied government employment to anyone with “membership in, affiliation with or sympathetic association with” communism (Truman 1946), and Soviet espionage became “one of the most monstrous betrayals in human history” (*Cold War* 1998; Daniel 1950). In 1950, Wisconsin Republican Senator Joseph McCarthy claimed to possess the names of over 200 communist infiltrators in the US State Department (McCarthy 1950).⁵⁰ He blamed the Soviets’ nuclear capability and China’s new communist regime on communist infiltration into US government (*Cold War* 1998, 13:50).⁵¹ McCarthy claimed that “the great difference between” the “western Christian world and the atheistic communist world” was not political but “moral,” and “no people who believe in a god” could “exist side by side with their communistic state.” According to McCarthy, the United States was “engaged in a final, all out battle between

50. McCarthy claimed the State Department was “thoroughly infested with communists” (McCarthy 1950).

51. In response to a note McCarthy sent to Truman in which he claimed to possess the names of 57 communists in the State Department, Truman called his claims untrue and insolent. He also called McCarthy unfit to work in the government and said he was “very sure that the people of Wisconsin are very sorry to be represented by a person who has as little sense of responsibility [as McCarthy]” (National Archives 2014).

communistic atheism and Christianity” (McCarthy 1950). McCarthy transformed communism from an existential but external threat into a morally repugnant conspiratorial bogeyman that had already burrowed into American society.

In the same year that McCarthy burst onto the scene, American newspapers reported the arrests of communist spies, the United States went to war in Korea, and the fear of nuclear annihilation steadily increased. Congress required “communist organizations” to register with the attorney general and established boards to investigate anyone they deemed “subversive” (International Security Act of 1950).⁵² Hoover wanted to “round up and detain 12,000 of the most dangerous men and women in his files” (Schrecker 2004, 1049), and loyalty oaths became commonplace. According to historian Ellen Schrecker, PhD (2004, 1043), McCarthyism “began in Washington D.C., and spread to the rest of the country. The federal government was the crucial actor ... its activities transformed the Communist [P]arty from an unpopular political group into a perceived threat to the American way of life.” The movement did not begin with McCarthy, however. He was not “the inventor, but the galvanic force, the inheritor, of a kind of rhetoric that had been growing in American politics for over a generation (Glazer, Lewis, and Tanenhaus 2004, 26).

Recognizing that Americans were traversing a slippery slope, Truman attempted to calm the storm. He warned of police-state-style tactics and vetoed the McCarran Act (International Security Act), but it re-passed Congress the very next day (Griffith 1971,

52. Senator Pat McCarran was the act’s chief proponent. He served as chairman of the Senate Judiciary Committee and leader of a coalition of conservative Republicans and Democrats (Griffith 1971, 27–28). The McCarran Act passed the Senate with a vote of 70–7 (29).

27; Truman 1950).⁵³ Truman had hoped that his religious rhetoric and the anti-communism movement would unite the nation toward common global goals. Instead, anti-communist hysteria threatened to tear the country apart from within. McCarthy became a voice for the radical right, and other republicans followed his lead. He called Truman a “sounding board” for communist propaganda (“Communists in the State Department” 2014), and Democrats came under pressure to support McCarthy’s movement for fear of being called unpatriotic (Griffith 1971, 27). America fell deeper into anti-communist hysteria as the government jailed Communist Party leaders, the FBI encouraged people to spy on their friends, protests broke out across the nation, educators lost their jobs for teaching about socialism, and even the Girl Scouts suffered accusations (*Cold War* 1998, 14:56–18:20; Craig and Logevall 2012, 125). For Americans, “one communist” in the US government was “one communist too many”(McCarthy 1952). At his height, 65% of republicans backed McCarthy (Glazer, Lewis, and Tanenhaus 2004, 26), and—though he had only a small group of ardent supporters (Griffith 1971, 26)—he became a demagogue who “reigned over Washington” (Craig and Logevall 2012, 124).

Although he detested McCarthy, Dwight D. Eisenhower needed his support to win the 1952 presidential election (*Cold War* 1998, 18:53). Amidst anti-communist hysteria and a religious revival, Eisenhower would turn Truman’s hopes for a state–religion partnership into a “direct identification with, if not embodiment of, religion itself” (Kirby 2013, 33:30). Eisenhower and his redbaiter running mate, Richard Nixon, campaigned on bearing “spiritual and intellectual arms against an alien army of communist ideas” (*Cold War* 1998, 16:45). Eisenhower began to hold private meetings

53. In response to the McCarran Act, Truman (1950) stated, “Legislation with these consequences is not necessary to meet the real dangers which communism presents to our free society. Those dangers are serious, and must be met. But this bill would hinder us, not help us, in the meeting of them.”

with Billy Graham, whose incredible fame had gained him massive social and political influence. Eisenhower had always endorsed religious belief—as reflected in his 1952 statement, “our form of government has no sense unless it is founded in a deeply felt religious faith, and I don't care what it is” (Eisenhower 1952), but Graham encouraged him to actually define his faith (Forsberg 2012). Under Graham’s influence, Eisenhower got baptized in his wife’s Presbyterian church shortly after taking office (Forsberg 2012; Preston 2012, 367).

Graham launched a six-week prayer campaign in Washington, D.C. that inspired House and Senate members to introduce a national day of prayer “on which the people of the United States may turn to God in prayer and meditation at churches, in groups, and as individuals” (Ronald 2014). Christian morality had become the ultimate weapon against the godless, communist threat, and America was set to define itself as a truly Christian nation. In 1953, the Knights of Columbus sent a resolution to the President, Vice President, Speaker of the House, and all of Congress, suggesting the addition “under God” to the Pledge of Allegiance.⁵⁴ Shortly thereafter, politicians introduced at least 17 bills to amend the pledge. Democrat Louis Rabaut framed his resolution as a strike against communism and a declaration of the true meaning of patriotism.⁵⁵ Francis Bellamy, a Christian socialist, had written the original pledge in 1892 as a means to re-ignite a sense of patriotism in American culture and as a sign of national solidarity after the American Civil War (Baer 1992), but according to Professor John Baer (1992), Bellamy would not have supported the “under God” addition since church-based racial

54. The Knights of Columbus was “the largest organization of Roman Catholic laymen in America” (Cloud 2004, 325).

55. Rabaut introduced House Joint Resolution 243, which became law in 1954 and added “under God” to the Pledge of Allegiance (H.J. Res 243 1954).

and political bigotry influenced his decision to write a pledge for “equality, liberty, and justice for all.” As pastor Canipe (2003, 320) explained, however, “at the most basic level in 1954, ‘under God’ meant ‘anti-communist.’”

Though it lay dormant in Congress for nearly a year, Eisenhower signed the resolution (Canipe 2003, 314–15; Cloud 2004, 325–26). Upon amending the pledge to include a religious expression, Eisenhower emphatically stated:

From this day forward, the millions of our school children will daily proclaim in every city and town, every village and rural school house, the dedication of our nation and our people to the Almighty. To anyone who truly loves America, nothing could be more inspiring than to contemplate this rededication of our youth, on each school morning, to our country's true meaning. (Eisenhower 1954b)

Eisenhower “freely associated God and Country with one another and encouraged others to do the same” (Canipe 2003, 313). “The implicit connection between Christianity and anti-communism accurately reflected prevailing popular sentiment” and “for most Americans, it seemed, religion and patriotism (which at the time was virtually synonymous with anti-communism) simply represented two sides of the same coin.” (312). Professor Markku Ruotsila, PhD (2013, 1027), called churches in the 1950s “the most influential venue in shaping political views of citizens.” Christian fundamentalist influence prevailed in government propaganda—which taught Americans the spiritual responsibility of citizenship, how to be moral members of society, and to be on the lookout for communist bogeymen—while Eisenhower mandated that cabinet meetings open with a prayer.⁵⁶

McCarthy continued pointing his finger and began spreading a new conspiracy theory that claimed a communist network across the United States was actively

56. See AFIF-5 (1950), *Communism* (1952), *How to Say No [Moral Maturity]* (1951), *The American Adventure* (1955), and Kirby (2013, 34:20).

corrupting American youth by filling the US education system with teachers who took orders directly from Moscow (*Point of Order* 1964, 5:02). Hoover and the FBI tried to purge American culture of anything they viewed as subversive and even launched an attack on the British-born movie star Charlie Chaplin for “grave moral charges and allegations of communist associations.” Hoover ultimately booted the tramp during Chaplin’s overseas tour by revoking his US reentry permit because of his “views of personal morality” and “contemptuous attitude toward American Patriotism” (Sbardellati and Shaw 2003, 496–97).⁵⁷ The FBI viewed celebrity communist sympathizers as more influential to the rest of the world than the words of Jesus Christ (500). McCarthy spread similar ideas by claiming that:

Christianity, which has been in existence for two-thousand years, has not converted—convinced—nearly as many people as this communist brutalitarianism has enslaved in one hundred and six years. And they’re not going to stop. (*Point of Order* 1964, 6:00–6:23)

The Manichean discourse that dominated the decade had begun to turn the forces of “good” upon each other. The FBI and HUAC investigated communist subversion within churches after Christian fundamentalists accused liberal Christians of being “Russia’s most effective fifth column in America” (Ruotsila 2013, 1020–24). Christian politicians began to reinvent the very origins of the United States. They simplified the religious views of the Founding Fathers and traded the doctrines of the Enlightenment for religious scriptures. Graham compared the Constitution to the Bible and Hoover claimed that “the American ideal, from its inception, based itself on a fundamental belief in God” (Aiello 2005). Nixon touted Western-style freedom as impossible without Christianity, Rabaut exclaimed—from the House floor—that America was “a Christian nation which

57. Sbardellati and Shaw (2003) quoted from FBI memo no. 100-127090-186, CHARLIE CHAPLIN, FBI, from G.H. Scatterday to Alex Rosen, dated July 12, 1962.

believes in God; a nation founded upon and imbued with a fundamental faith in our Creator” (Aiello 2005), and Eisenhower himself emphatically stated:

Without God there could be no American form of government, nor an American way of life. Recognition of the Supreme Being is the first—the most basic—expression of Americanism. Thus the Founding Fathers saw it, and thus, with God’s help, it will continue to be. (Eisenhower 1955)

While the Manichean discourse continued to form a new American patriotism, Joe McCarthy finally lost his battle. The Senate condemned McCarthy, ending his career, after his accusations spun out of control. He named presidents, senators, generals, and the US Army itself as communist sympathizers or Soviet puppets. His attacks on the Senate’s policies and procedures ultimately led to his downfall (Glazer, Lewis, and Tanenhaus 2004, 23) but he was not censured for his anti-communist fervor but rather for conduct that was “unbecoming a Member of the United States Senate” (Griffith 1971, 34). Even with McCarthy out of the picture, the Senate continued its anti-communist campaigns. Historian Robert Griffith, PhD (1971), described the continuing assault on American civil liberties when he wrote:

Prodded by the Eisenhower administration both Senate and House quickly approved legislation to strip citizenship from persons convicted of conspiracy to advocate the violent overthrow of government, to make peacetime espionage a capital offense, to require communist organizations to register all printing equipment, to grant immunity to witnesses before courts, grand juries and congressional committees in order to compel testimony, to increase the penalties for harboring fugitives and jumping bail and to broaden and redefine espionage and sabotage laws. (32)

By 1954, the Communist Control Act had outlawed the Communist Party, and soon-to-be-Vice-President Hubert Humphrey introduced a bill that called communism an “agency

of hostile foreign power.” Humphrey declared, “I do not intend to be a half patriot. I will not be lukewarm.” (Griffin 1971, 32–33).⁵⁸

In his 1954 state of the union address, Eisenhower recommended that Congress enact legislation to strip citizenship from anyone who *conspired* to advocate the overthrow of the US government (Canipe 2003, 312, emphasis added; Eisenhower 1954a). He later signed into law a resolution that established the national motto as “In God We Trust” (Cloud 2004, 326). Senator Ralph Flanders proposed another constitutional amendment that stated “this Nation devoutly recognizes the authority and law of Jesus Christ, Savior and Ruler of nations, through whom are bestowed the blessings of Almighty God” (Haraldsson 2011).⁵⁹ The American Legion hosted “Back to God” television specials in which Hoover called communists “anti-god” while encouraging parents to send their children to church (Canipe 2003, 314). The fight had slowly become less about communist infiltration and more about the definition of patriotism. By 1954, 79% of Americans attended church while 96% claimed to believe in God (312).⁶⁰ By 1957, 85% of Americans could identify Billy Graham and his religious affiliation (Aiello 2005).⁶¹ In 1958, *The Washington Post* reported “believers in God” to

58. Griffith (1971, 33) quoted from *Congressional Record*, 83rd Cong. 2nd Sess., August 12, 1954, 14210–34 and August 17, 1954, 14727.

59. Flanders’ amendment did not pass Congress. Kirby (2013, 34:50) explained that Congress feared that the bill would drive a wedge between the various faiths. They sought to ally all religions against communism, not exclusively Christianity.

60. Canipe (2003) cited *The Gallup Poll: Public Opinion, 1935–1971*, Vol. 2, 1949–1958 (New York: Random House, 1972) 1253 and 1293. He provided comparative data to show that belief in God may not have changed, although church attendance did. He suggested that “religious practice and social expression was much more visible during those years [1950s]” (312), as church attendance became somewhat linked to patriotic duty.

61. Aiello (2005) used data from Gallup 1490–91.

be the “Reds’ undoing” (“Believers in God Called Reds’ Undoing,” 1958).⁶² The strongly Manichean narrative used to describe global affairs had enabled organizations like Christian Crusade, the Christian Anti-Communist Crusade, and the National Association for Evangelicals to adopt anti-communism and Christianity-based patriotism as strategic tools for political and social influence (Aiello 2005). The anti-communist movement had popularized religious belief to the point that it could define the nation. Conspiracism kept it in charge.

Accusations of communist activities, guilt by association, and blacklisting continued to spiral out of control, but policy makers began to enact judicial reforms to protect the rights of American citizens (Cole 2003, 7–8). The legal and political changes, combined with the civil-rights movement of the 1960s, inspired a Christian-fundamentalist backlash. The heavily Manichean discourse of the previous 30 years had created an atmosphere that fostered absolutist ideologies. It had also given them a popular voice. Christianity had become an essential aspect of American patriotism—and a government allegedly sympathetic to communism simply could not be Christian, patriotic, or truly American.

The civil-rights movement brought race issues to the table as well, and anti-communism became a vehicle for racial extremists. After a conspiracism-fueled rise to power, Christian fundamentalists believed—or so they claimed—that the US government had been infiltrated by the agents of communism. New Christianity-based right-wing movements targeted US policies and institutions in their propaganda. They also labeled

62. The article reported testimony before the HUAC: Dr. Lowery, chairman of the Foundation for Religious Action in the Social and Civil Order, called for a united front of religious leaders to wage a “war of ideas” to “strangle communism by cutting off its flow of intellectual converts” (“Believers in God Called Reds’ Undoing,” 1958).

civil-rights leaders “Communist infiltrators” (Brister and Kollars 2011, 52; *Cold War* 1998; Merkl and Weinberg 1997, 10–12).

The John Birch Society, arguably the father of the Patriot movement, warned of a “Soviet Negro Republic” being formed inside the United States that was, of course, manipulated and controlled by Moscow (Terry 2013). The organization was founded in 1958 as a populist movement aimed at eliminating communist influence, but it quickly targeted Martin Luther King Jr. and other civil-rights advocates (Brister and Kollars 2011, 52). At the same time, many politicians continued to support staunch anti-communism as well as Christian fundamentalism in US government. Senator Barry Goldwater was a leader in the right-wing political movement throughout the Cold War. He advocated an aggressive posture against communism and claimed that America “must go on the offensive” because it “can’t win by merely trying to hold [its] own” (Craig and Logevall 2012, 231). According to Goldwater and many who supported him, “extremism in defense of liberty is no vice” (Bio 2015). This was the anti-communist mentality that inspired Richard Hofstadter’s essay “The Paranoid Style in American Politics” (1964). Many anti-communists had developed a strong Manichean worldview. Anti-communism had become a way of life—and they found a conspiratorial bogeyman lurking around every corner.

For decades, Americans had suffered on multiple fronts. After World War II and Korea, they were caught in a battle of ideologies—and they also had to deal with the threat of nuclear war. The Christian nation had emerged from a mixture of fear, religious-political exploitation, and an American identity crisis. Throughout the Cold War, fear, anti-communism, and Christian fundamentalism swayed American society, politics, and

diplomacy, both foreign and domestic. America found itself in a string of proxy wars around the globe and in the middle of a nuclear arms race (Herring 2011, 661–914). Some American leaders tried to ease tensions through détente, but anti-communists refused to play nice with the atheistic others (Craig and Logevall 2012, 240–312). At home, religious and racist extremists became increasingly virulent in their attacks against civil-rights advocates and the federal government (Belew 2012; *Cold War 1998*). For “true” patriots, the US government had failed to defeat the communist others. In fact, it was in cahoots with them.

Patriots of Conspiracy

Even in its infancy, the Patriot movement employed conspiracy-theory-laced fear. Professor Stuart Wright, PhD (2013), claimed that “it cannot be extricated from the antecedent conditions of the Cold War and the civil rights era that posed the dual threats of communist subversion and race equality to Southern elites and right-wing groups” (46). As a product of anti-communist hysteria and popular Manichean discourse, a conspiracy-based narrative was the natural way to communicate. Christian Identity leaders, who were deeply anti-Semitic and racially motivated, led the charge against progressive social change.⁶³ The John Birch Society formed political partnerships with McCarthyites and rallied public support against “enemies in Washington ... [and] the State Department” (54). Meanwhile, other groups nurtured growing racist, anti-government, anti-globalist sentiment by attacking civil rights, the federal government,

63. Christian Identity members believe that white Christians are God’s chosen people and advocate criminal action under divine authority. Christian Identity leaders viewed the Christian Patriot movement as a way to unite right-wing extremist groups seeking “strength in numbers” (CJES 2010, 1.2).

and the international system while propagating rumors of Jewish plots to control the world (Brister and Kollars 2011, 52).

With a rich history of militant extremism dating back to the Civil War era, Ku Klux Klan white supremacist groups reinforced anti-globalism and anti-communism with anti-Semitic propaganda.⁶⁴ Echoing the Russian forgery, *The Protocols of the Elders of Zion*—which had inspired anti-Semitism for nearly a century—⁶⁵ right-wing extremists claimed that Communist-Jewish-banker elites secretly controlled the world’s major governments. Historian Stephen Atkins, PhD (2011), pointed out that the United Klans of America (UKA) “earned a reputation for violent acts” which their leader, Robert Shelton, justified by “equating the civil-rights movement with communism” (18). The UKA’s main goal was to stop the civil-rights movement in the South, but they also promoted Christian fundamentalism-inspired anti-Semitism and anti-globalism. As Shelton explained, “if a Jewish person is a Communist person we should not be considered anti-Semitic for exposing this person. And many Jews have been found in the Communist conspiracy” (18).⁶⁶ Shelton also began spreading what he called One-Worldism in the 1960s. As a precursor to many of today’s anti-globalist conspiracy theories, One-Worldism blamed the entire world’s problems on Wall Street investment banks that were allegedly controlled by Jews and Communists (18).

Fueled by religious, conspiracist, and patriotic beliefs, Christian extremist groups planned to take back the Christian Nation—and its government—from the communist,

64. After the Civil War in 1866, bored ex-Confederate soldiers founded the Ku Klux Klan (KKK) in Pulaski Tennessee. It has evolved into many forms under various names and is still active today (Atkins 2011, Chapter 1; George and Wilcox 1992, 29–30).

65. For more information about *The Protocols of the Elders of Zion*, see Aaronovitch (2010).

66. Atkins (2011) quoted Shelton from an interview with journalist Margaret Long (1964).

globalist, and corporate elites. Throughout the 1960s such groups became increasingly militaristic. Robert DePugh and his underground group, the Minutemen, had formed a paramilitary organization because of their fear of an imminent communist attack. Concerned about US citizens' ability to defend themselves, they planned to "become familiar with guerrilla tactics," to practice maneuvers, and to cache weapons and ammunition throughout their operational areas (Wright 2013, 58). The Minutemen operated in small cells and kept their identities secret in case of a communist invasion. DePugh criticized the John Birch Society for "acquiescing to the political system" (59), and the Minutemen became "notorious" for their paramilitary activities, weapons stockpiling, and claim to be 10,000-members strong. Though the FBI tracked less than 1000 members, their paramilitary nature and extremist rhetoric caused major concern. The increase in paramilitary activities and racially motivated, widespread domestic terrorism forced the FBI to intervene. By 1965, the KKK had conducted 225 bombings and over 1000 acts of racial violence, yet law enforcement officials had made no arrests (Atkins 2011, 22). As Atkins (2011) explained, "J. Edgar Hoover had little sympathy for the civil rights movement. Political pressure from the Johnson administration, however, forced Hoover to become more receptive to intervention" (23). The FBI had to rely on undercover agents because so many local law enforcement officers were members of or sympathetic to the Klan's cause (22–24).⁶⁷

In 1966 DePugh started a political wing of the Minutemen called the Patriotic Party, which came to be known as the "armed division of the John Birch Society" (Janson

67. The FBI initiated a new counterintelligence program, COINTERPRO, which targeted right-wing organizations in the South, most of which had ties to the KKK. The program was highly successful in decreasing KKK activity (Atkins 2011, 24), but it also increased Patriot paranoia and distrust for the federal government.

and Eisman 1963, 125 quoted in Wright 2013, 60). Later that year, DePugh and other Minutemen were charged with conspiracy to violate the National Firearms Act for illegal possession of machine guns. After they fled the authorities, the FBI raided one of their safe houses and found weapons, silencers, bombs, and grenades. DePugh and company were finally caught and went to prison, and the Minutemen dissolved, but their story catalyzed a new type of movement.

DePugh's Minutemen inspired a number of paramilitary groups, such as the Sons of Liberty, the Christian Soldiers, and the Soldiers of the Cross. Many of the organizations had "overlapping membership in the Ku Klux Klan and the National States Rights Party" (Wright 2013, 61), and their members consisted of a "striking range of racists and Anti-Semites" including "veterans of ... fascist groups from the 1930s" (Carter 1998 quoted in Wright 2013, 61). Christian fundamentalists continually reinforced the Christian-Nation version of American patriotism by driving a wedge between national pride and support for the "globalist, corporate-controlled" federal government. William Potter Gale was heavily involved in the movement and, as Wright (2013, 62) described, was "the key figure who bridged old Cold War framing and new threats in an emergent Patriot ideology that ... served as a base to mobilize insurgents in the 1980s and 1990s." Gale and Henry Lamont Beach created the *Posse Comitatus*, "Power of the County," as an anti-government organization that rejected federal jurisdiction and viewed the local sheriff as "the supreme governmental figure" from which "all governmental authority flowed" (Atkins 2011, 196–97).⁶⁸ *Posse Comitatus*

68. *Posse Comitatus* claimed to derive its legal rights from the "United States Constitution, Magna Carte, Bible, Common Law, and the Articles of Confederation" (CJES 2010, 1.0).

combined religious, paramilitary, and strongly anti-government propaganda to become the father of the Christian Patriots.⁶⁹

With ties to the Birch Society and the Minutemen (Brister and Kollars 2011, 52; Wright 2013, 61), Gale was well connected to other extreme groups, and his *Posse Comitatus* represented “a pivotal component in the development of the Patriot movement” (Wright 2013, 63). For Gale, “America’s enemy” was communism and the “International Jewish conspiracy” (Newton 2007, 152 quoted in Brister and Kollars 2011, 52). As Paul Brister and Nina Kollars (2011) explained:

By adopting a diverse set of enemies—all bound in a complex conspiracy to create a new world order—Gale offered common ground upon which all right-wing extremist organisations [sic] could rally. Although their reasons varied, multiple right-wing organisations [sic] came together and agreed upon three core concepts: a re-dedication to individual gun rights, a fear of a one-world government (especially a Jewish-controlled one); and a recognition that a vanguard party should be established to defend American ideals. (53)

Gale and the Posse began to concentrate less on the communist threat and more on anti-government and New-World-Order conspiracy theories.

The Farm Crisis of the late 1970s and early 1980s brought new membership and skills—in the form of demolitions and technological expertise—to the Posse and other groups (Brister and Kollars 2011, 54; Wright 2013, Chapter 4). As farmers joined right-wing-extremist organizations, the Posse blamed their financial troubles on the New World Order and the Zionist Occupied Government (ZOG). They also taught seminars on “constitutional law” and spread conspiracy theories about the “truth” behind “paper dollars,” the abandonment of the gold standard, and ZOG control of the legal system

69. Brister and Kollars (2011) define the Christian Patriot movement as “a loose affiliation of armed groups linked by a belief that the federal government has intentionally undermined the founding principles of liberty, democracy, and Christianity” whose aim is the “marginalization or destruction of its ‘enemies’ – immigrants, Jews, African Americans, or the American government at large” (50).

(Brister and Kollars 2011, 54–55). Soon Tax Protesters, Sovereign Citizens, and Wise Use movement groups emerged throughout the nation, and—although each movement claimed a slightly different cause—they were deeply rooted in Christian fundamentalism, anti-government forms of patriotism, and paranoia (Atkins 2011; Berger 2012; Berlet and Lyons 2000; CJES 2010; Johnson 2012; Lenz and Potok 2014).⁷⁰

In the decade to follow, Patriot groups took various forms in response to government policies and anti-government or anti-Semitic conspiracy theories. New militant organizations such as the Aryan Nations, Texas Light Infantry (TLI), and The Covenant, Sword, and Arm of the Lord (CSA) spawned different types of extremist groups that opposed everything from federal-government authority to income taxes, gun-control reform, and environmental-protection programs (Brister 2010; Brister and Kollars 2011; Berger 2012). The Aryan Nations focused on building enough membership to gain political power (Atkins 2011, 142), while the TLI maintained “battalions” that conducted infantry-style training exercises, which even included occasional airborne operations (Berger 2012, 7). The CSA built a 250-acre compound where it “specialized in automatic weapons conversion, survivalist skills, explosive devices, marksmanship, and special tactics” and conducted explosives and live fire exercises to “emphasize real conditions and practice mock assassinations” (CJES 2010, 1.6). Roger Moore and Thomas Posey—who had formed the anti-communist Civilian Materiel Assistance (CMA) organization—reconfigured the CMA into a “survivalist-type” anti-government group of 700 members and traveled the country distributing guns, ammunition, and propaganda at gun shows

70. Many groups reject conventional Christian views, and some mix Christianity with paganism. Some of the white supremacist and neo-Nazi groups are Odinists or followers of Asatru who worship the Norse gods Wotan or Odin (Weinberg 2013, 19). The Tax Protestors and Sovereign Citizens follow *Posse Comitatus* “constitutional law” teachings, and the Wise Use movement rejects federal or state land management as “treasonous to true Americans” (CJES 2010, 1.16–1.18).

nationwide (Berger 2012, 7).⁷¹ Concerned about rumors of the ZOG's plans to destroy citizens' rights, relinquish sovereignty to the UN, and confiscated firearms, the Patriots prepared to launch a wave of violence. The CMA, Aryan Nations, TLI, and *Posse Comitatus* would join forces to create the perfect storm of conspiracy-inspired Patriot terrorism.

The Patriots heavily propagated a book called *The Turner Diaries* (1978)—a conspiracy-based, racist work of fiction written by white supremacist, William Luther Pierce. The book, which the “Patriots heralded as a prophetic text” (Wright 2013, 113), depicted a future struggle between the ZOG and the white race in which the ZOG planned to prohibit and confiscate firearms, forcing a group called the *Organization* into action. The *Organization* robbed banks, murdered agents, bombed buildings and eventually detonated a nuclear weapon to incite a race war and take back control of the nation. *The Turner Diaries* became known as the “Bible of the Patriot movement,” and it inspired Patriot terrorists to try bringing its pages to life (Atkins 2011, 102–06; Berger 2012, 5–6; Brister and Kollars 2011, 58; CJES 2010, 1.3–1.5).

Energized by *The Protocols of the Elders of Zion* and *The Turner Diaries*, a group of Patriots called the Order, AKA the Silent Brotherhood, sought to “destabilize the U.S. government with the intent of forcing it to allow a white homeland in the Pacific Northwest” (Atkins 2011, 157).⁷² Under Posse influence and Aryan Nation guidance, members of the Order robbed banks, conducted assassinations, bombed buildings, and

71. The CMA provided assistance to the anti-communist contras in Central America during the 1980s, and, according to rumors, US military intelligence and the CIA provided support to the CMA (Berger 2012, 6–7).

72. Robert Jay Mathews founded the Order in 1983 after reading *The Turner Diaries* and converting to Odinism. In the 1970s he and a group of Mormon survivalists had created the anti-communist group, the Sons of Liberty, to fight against the Jewish-International conspiracy as detailed in *The Protocols of the Elders of Zion*.

plotted attacks using weapons of mass destruction. They stole approximately \$4 million, which they distributed to other militant group leaders such as Frazier Glenn Miller, head of the paramilitary White Patriot Party; and Klansman, Aryan Nations ambassador, and militia leader, Louis Beam (Atkins 2011, 157–61, 222–24; Belew 2012, 214-18, 230-38; Brister and Kollars 2011, 55; Maddow 2014b). The Order became the elite unit of the Patriot movement and other groups followed their lead. Some Patriots committed violence while others used shortwave radio broadcasts and printed media to gain support, recruit new members, and spread anti-government propaganda. They frequented gun shows across the country, offering videotapes, books, pamphlets, and flyers and trained militia groups dedicated to defending against federal tyranny.

The new wave of domestic terrorism and increasing extremist activity drew the federal government's attention. Federal agents raided several Patriot compounds and uncovered stockpiles of assault rifles, machine guns, plastic explosives, hand grenades, improvised explosive devices, anti-tank rockets, land mines, thousands of rounds of ammunition, and canisters of sodium cyanide meant for poisoning water supplies (Brister and Kollars 2011, 55–56; CJES 2010, 1.6; Johnson 2012, Chapter 3). After agents discovered the CSA's plot to bomb the Alfred P. Murrah Federal Building in Oklahoma City, Patriot groups began to tone down their discourse and solidify their alliances. *Posse Comitatus* had been labeled a terrorist organization so it rebranded itself as the *Christian Patriots*. It “honed in on the idea that the United States government was secretly planning a war on its citizens,” complete with rumors of “black helicopters and UN concentration

camps” (Brister 2010, 181).⁷³ The CMA and TLI hosted a convention sponsored by *Soldier of Fortune* magazine to “create a nationwide coalition strong enough to stand up to the full might of the federal government” through cross-membership and increased communication. According to its leaders, “the seed was planted by the Order” and the Patriots would “make it grow” (Berger 2012, 8–10).

By the early 1990s, the increased pressure from law enforcement agencies, combined with the post–Cold War militarization of police forces, reinforced the Patriots’ paranoia. Furthermore, President George H.W. Bush used the phrase “New World Order” to describe the international alliance in the Persian Gulf, and the Patriots commandeered his speech as proof for anti-globalist conspiracy theories (CJES 2010, 1.9). The Bush administration’s gun-control reform prompted rumors about a coming police state, and the Patriots presented the War on Drugs as a front for the disarmament of the American people (Wright 2013, Chapter 5). As the federal government tried to prevent terrorist access to automatic weapons, the Christian Patriots stockpiled weapons, ammunition, and supplies. It was a feedback loop of epic proportions. FBI undercover agents infiltrated the movement and found themselves steeped in a world of paranoia, conspiracy theories, and religious, racist, anti-government propaganda.

In 1992, US Marshals botched a reconnaissance mission on a white-separatist compound owned by Patriot Randy Weaver at Ruby Ridge, Idaho. After an intense shootout and a multi-day standoff, Weaver’s wife, his son, and a US Marshal lay dead. Patriot activists Bo Gritz and Jack McLamb arrived on the scene and talked Weaver into

73. Posse member, Gordon Kahl, refused to pay taxes and taught others to do the same. When US Marshals attempted to arrest him, Kahl killed two and wounded four others. He escaped and “declared open war on the federal government” until law enforcement officers killed him during another shootout four months later. Kahl’s fellow Patriots called him the “first martyr of the Second American Revolution” (Atkins 2011, 201–02).

surrendering. Meanwhile, hundreds of Patriot protesters gathered around the area holding signs with anti-government and anti-Semitic messages. The Ruby Ridge shootout sent shockwaves throughout the extremist community. For many, it meant a declaration of war and solidified fears of the coming police state (Berger 2012, 13–15; Wright 2013 144–52).

Shortly after Ruby Ridge, prominent leaders of the various Patriot groups held two major conventions that would revolutionize the movement. In Benton, Tennessee, 150 Patriots from the American Pistol and Rifle Association (APRA) and the CMA conducted firearms and live-fire assault training exercises and exchanged weapons and equipment. In attendance were APRA leader John Grady and Bo Gritz, who recounted his experience at Ruby Ridge. Gritz “predicted that the government would declare a national emergency by 1994 and seize everyone’s guns, just as described in *The Turner Diaries*, after which the population would be forced to receive the ‘mark of the beast.’” Grady followed with a speech about the “coming ‘chastisement’ of America by God” and encouraged the crowd to prepare for death and “hope for the opportunity to ‘die as martyrs’” (Berger 2012, 14–15). Later, 160 Patriot leaders—including Louis Beam, John Trochmann, Larry Pratt, and Richard Butler—met at the “Rocky Mountain Rendezvous,” in Estes Park, Colorado (Combs, Combs, and Marsh 2005; Wright 2013, 149–51).⁷⁴ In what Paul Brister (2010, 181) described as a “circus of the bizarre, neo-Nazis, survivalists, Christian Identity adherents, militia members, Klansmen, and tax-protestors”

74. John Trochmann would form the largest American militia, the Militia of Montana, which focused on targeting the New World Order (Atkins 2011, 227-29). Larry Pratt, Executive Director of Gun Owners of America, publicly promoted armed militias and became known as the father of the Militia movement (Wright 2013, 124). Richard Butler, who founded the Christian Defense League with William Potter Gale in the late 1950s, became the head of the Aryan Nations and worked with white supremacist David Duke (Wright 2013, 62-63).

birthed the modern Militia movement, fueled by New-World-Order conspiracy theories, Christian apocalyptic fundamentalism, and the incident at Ruby Ridge (Johnson 2012, 53). The new militias would emphasize “leaderless resistance” and guerrilla warfare, and they would replace the old communist enemy with the federal government. According to Klansman Louis Beam, “Communism now represents a threat to no one in the United States ... while federal tyranny represents a threat to *everyone*” (Beam 1992 1, quoted in Wright 2013, 50).

Six months later, the Bureau of Alcohol, Tobacco, Firearms, and Explosives (ATF) launched a paramilitary raid on the Branch Davidian Compound in Waco, Texas. The Branch Davidians were a religious cult obsessed with end-times prophecies and had prepared for a coming war by stockpiling massive amounts of weapons and ammunition. After receiving tips about their illegal weapons possession and possible child abuse, the ATF planned a raid on the Mount Carmel compound. A firefight ensued. After a 51-day standoff, the compound burned to the ground and 80 people were dead, including 76 Branch Davidians and four ATF agents (plus another 20 agents wounded). Among the debris, federal agents recovered nearly 300 firearms, including close to 50 machine guns (Atkins 2011, 218–19; Johnson 2012, 53–62; Wright 2013, 152–65). According to Atkins (2011):

Waco galvanized the antigovernment forces in the United States far beyond earlier incidents. To them, Waco was part of a government conspiracy to take away American rights. In their view, it was an attack on gun rights and religious freedom. Coming so soon after Ruby Ridge, it confirmed to the antigovernment extremists that the federal government was lined up against them. (219–20)

Within five years, the number of right-wing militias operating in the United States grew from around a dozen to over 800 (Combs, Combs, and Marsh 2005).

In the wake of Ruby Ridge, Waco, and a number of other raids on Patriot compounds, Congress passed the Brady Bill in 1993 and the Violent Crime Control and Law Enforcement Act of 1994.⁷⁵ Enraged Patriots viewed the new gun-control measures as straight from the pages of *The Turner Diaries* and began an insurgency campaign against the New World Order. Christian Patriot leaders combined narratives from the various Patriot factions and militias to present “the assumption that a war with the government was already under way.” Their total numbers approached four million (Wright 2013, 166–68). They quickly propagated rumors of foreign troops coming to US soil to enforce the new gun laws (CJES 2010, 1.9), and the disarmament conspiracy theories prompted Patriots like Timothy McVeigh to move from the “‘propaganda stage’ to the ‘action stage’” (Michel and Herbeck 2001, 159–61 quoted in Wright 2013, 178).

On April 19, 1995—after being radicalized by *The Turner Diaries*, befriending the CMA and TLI, associating with the Christian Identity movement, and being outraged by the incidents at Ruby Ridge and Waco—McVeigh carried out the CSA’s plan to bomb the Murrah building in Oklahoma City (OKC).⁷⁶ In the largest pre-9/11 act of domestic terrorism in US history, McVeigh detonated a nearly-5000 pound ammonium nitrate bomb, killing 162 people and injuring 432 others (Atkins 2011, 237; Berger 2012; Hafez and Rasmussen 2010, 19). The bombing caused a rift in the Patriot movement that undid much of the cooperation and coordination its leaders had created. Some Patriots “forged

75. The Brady Bill (Handgun Violence Prevention Act) imposed a 5-day waiting period for handgun purchases in states without acceptable systems for background checks. See <https://www.atf.gov/content/firearms/firearms-industry/brady-law>. The Crime Control Act increased law enforcement funding, banned assault weapons, and increased sentencing options. See <https://www.ncjrs.gov/txtfiles/billfs.txt>.

76. McVeigh’s accomplices, Terry Nichols and Michael Fortier, aided him in planning and preparing for the bombing. McVeigh and Nichols robbed a quarry for explosives in Kansas. They also allegedly robbed a gun dealer for funds (Atkins 2011, 239).

ahead by committing new acts of violence” (Wright 2013, 194), while others pushed their movements underground and dropped their “Christian Patriot” labels in attempts to sever ties to McVeigh and his Christian Identity associates (Brister and Kollars 2011, 58). New rumors began to emerge, as some Patriots claimed that McVeigh was actually an undercover agent. According to the new conspiracy theories, the federal government had orchestrated the bombing as justification for martial law (Berger 2012, 21; Wright 2013, 194–95).

After OKC there was a temporary and violent spike in Patriot activity. Groups like the Militia of Montana, the Michigan Militia, the Washington State Militia, and the Viper Militia of Arizona remained highly active. Less than a year after the bombing, Patriots from militiamen and Sovereign Citizens to Klansmen and biker gangs attended an insurgency rally called Jubilation 1996 where they distributed propaganda that included manuals on the use of improvised explosive devices and chemical weapons. Meanwhile, the Freemen of Montana trained “upwards of 1,000 people” on *Posse Comitatus* philosophy and tactics before an 81-day stand off with FBI agents (Atkins 2011, 229–34; CJES 2010, 1.10–1.11). Later that year, militia leaders held the “Third Continental Congress” and planned to overthrow the US government (Atkins 2011, 233). As federal and state agencies targeted right-wing domestic terrorist organizations and arrested many of their leaders, raids on Patriot compounds produced large stockpiles of machine guns, ammunition, various types of explosives, homemade weapons like flamethrowers and cannons, and even chemical weapons from sodium cyanide to ricin and sarin nerve gas. Twenty states passed anti-militia laws and the media demonized the movement. By 1999, the Patriots were in drastic decline (CJES 2010, 1.12-1.15; Johnson

2012, 71). As Wright (2013) explained, they were “unable to mount an effective stand against allied state and third-party actors [and] the dispirited Patriot campaign gradually retreated in disarray ... the movement steadily demobilized” (195).

The Return of the Patriots

After the attacks of September 11th, 2001 the Patriot movement continued its decline. The external threat posed by international terrorist groups drew attention away from the federal government. As Wright (2013) explained, “the nation rallied behind the new war on terrorism that targeted al Qaeda and Muslim extremists in the wake of 9/11. New battle lines were drawn in the radically altered political environment, and the Patriot frame was divested of its meaning and resonance for right-wing audiences” (214). As 9/11 conspiracy theories began to emerge, the Patriots—at least initially—rejected the accusations (Atkins 2011, 234). Though some believed the attack was an inside job to justify martial law, most Patriot groups supported the Global War on Terrorism (GWOT),⁷⁷ and many simply traded the old communist bogeyman for an Islamic one.

History of religion scholar Arthur Buehler, PhD (2011), traced *Islamophobia* in the West to the beginning of the Cold War. The term “Islamophobia” first appeared in 1991 and describes “unfounded hostility towards Islam, and therefore fear or dislike of all or most Muslims” (651).⁷⁸ According to Buehler, after World War II the media had portrayed Israelis as heroes and Arabs as villains. By the 1970s, most Westerners equated Arabs with all Muslims and assumed them both to be “the bad guys” (641). After the

77. Many Patriots feared that the USA PATRIOT Act (2001) would grant the government the power to become a police state (Michael 2006, 222–24).

78. Buehler (2011, 651) cites the quoted definition of Islamophobia as found in the 1997 edition of the *Oxford English Dictionary*, defined therein by a 1997 Runnymede Trust report. He cites the term’s origin as being first mentioned in the February 1991 edition of *Insight* 4, no. 37.

collapse of Soviet communism, academics and politicians began pondering a potential—perhaps inevitable—clash between the Islamic world and the West (643).⁷⁹ Despite a multitude of reasons for conflict, the media presented most of the problems in Islamic countries as religiously inspired, and Islamophobia quickly spread through public rhetoric, religious organizations, and special interest groups (644–45). As they had done with communism in the early days of the Cold War, Christian fundamentalists presented Islam as an evil, conspiratorial force bent on destroying Christianity (Cimino 2005). Though Islamophobia is clearly present—and extremists have continually attacked Muslims in the United States since 9/11 (Johnson 2012, 320, Maddow 2014b)—the Patriots have once again shifted their focus to the US federal government. This time, however, the communists are not the infiltrators—the Muslims are.

After Barack Obama’s 2008 presidential election, the number of Patriot or militia-affiliated extremist groups rose dramatically (Morgenstern 2013). Although some extremists disliked him for strictly political or racial reasons,⁸⁰ Obama’s presidency sparked a host of new conspiracy theories that reinvigorated the Patriot movement. Right-wing propagandists presented Obama as everything from a puppet of the New World Order to a secret Muslim.⁸¹ Conspiracists constructed theories about the “Islamization of America” (Dyson 2012, 32), warned that Obama would enact new gun-control laws (Belew 2012, 416–22; SPLC 2010), and spun immigration reform as a plot to take jobs

79. Political scientist Samuel Huntington’s *Foreign Affairs* article and subsequent book, *The Clash of Civilizations*, predicted a coming war between Islam and the West, sparking media frenzies and increased Islamophobia (Buehler 2011, 643).

80. Within two years of Obama’s election, the white supremacist website, *stormfront.org*, nearly doubled its membership. It gained over 2,000 members the day after the election (Johnson 2012, 207).

81. The “Birther movement,” which claimed that Obama was not born in the United States and therefore not eligible to be president, became popular among the Patriots (Keller 2009, 8; SPLC 2010).

from white Christian Americans, to allow terrorists into the country (Toboni 2015), or to destroy US sovereignty (Keller 2009, 8). Soon Americans across the nation began hoarding weapons and ammunition (Johnson 2012, 225), and militias conducted armed patrols along the US-Mexico border (Nelson 2012; Toboni 2015).

Law enforcement officials reacted to threats on President Obama's life, confiscated stockpiles of weapons and explosives, foiled acts of domestic terrorism, and even recovered a dirty bomb in-the-making (Johnson 2012, Chapter 9; SPLC 2012, 31–34). In 2009, a leaked Department of Homeland Security (DHS) document made matters even worse. DHS wrote the report, *Rightwing Extremism: Current Economic and Political Climate Fueling Resurgence in Radicalization and Recruitment* (2009), as a situational awareness tool for law enforcement agencies. It identified a potential increase in right-wing-extremist activity, expressed concern over the recent volume of weapons and ammunition purchases, and listed veterans returning from the GWOT campaigns as likely targets for extremist radicalization and recruitment. DHS labeled the report “FOR OFFICIAL USE ONLY,” but someone quickly posted it on the Internet. The Patriots and the media erupted with anger. News pundits, politicians, and veterans groups—such as the American Legion and the Veterans of Foreign Wars—claimed that the report was offensive, reinforced disgruntled veteran stereotypes, and unfairly profiled the military. The backlash was so severe that DHS removed the report from its website and dismantled its team of analysts devoted to non-Islamic domestic terrorism (Belew 2012, 414–26; Johnson 2012, Chapter 14).

Since 2009, Patriot violence and militia activity has skyrocketed (Leinwand 2013; Rosenberg 2014; SPLC 2015a). Nearly every state has at least one militia group and most

states have many (Combs, Combs, and Marsh 2005). Some have formed strong relationships with Christian fundamentalist-isolationist communities and created paramilitary congregations, while others conduct coordinated military exercises in which militia members practice ambushes, sniper missions, close-quarters battle drills, and infantry tactics against opposition forces dressed to resemble federal agents. Some militia leaders even predict an inevitable war with the federal government. They are heavily armed, highly trained, and well connected.⁸²

In 2014, the Patriot militias demonstrated their willingness to mobilize against the federal government. After over 20 years and \$1 million in unpaid grazing fees, the Bureau of Land Management (BLM) and local police traveled to Sovereign Citizen Cliven Bundy's ranch in Bunkerville, Nevada to confiscate his cattle. After posting a message to Glenn Beck's website, in which Bundy claimed that federal agents were trespassing on his land, the militias responded in force. As Southern Poverty Law Center's Ryan Lenz and Mark Potok (2014) explained:

Within four days of his defiant comments on Beck's network, hundreds of heavily armed militia members had swarmed by the truckload to Bundy's corner of the desert, angry, armed, and ready to take on the federal government. (9)

Militia members from multiple states occupied fortified fighting positions with federal agents literally in their sights. The armed crowd of men and women—some with semi-automatic weapons and body armor—threatened federal employees as Patriot snipers lined hilltops and overpasses while crowds held signs “condemning the BLM as a

82. See Gellman (2010), Gunter (2012), Keller (2009), Lenz and Potok (2014), Nelson (2012), Sharrock (2010), and Toboni (2015). For an example of Patriot doctrine, see the *Field Manual of the Free Militia* (1994), which teaches militia members skills in firearm selection, communication strategies, equipment use, and guerrilla tactics while firmly inculcating Christianity-based theological justifications for war.

communist agent” (12). The local county sheriff on the scene told television news reporters that “the hair was up on the back of [his] neck ... there was a lot of firepower out there and it made [him] nervous. Anything could happen” (14). When Bundy ordered the “mob of angry antigovernment zealots fueled by conspiracy theories” to take back his cattle (9), BLM officials suspended the operation in order to protect federal employees. At “the Battle of Bunkerville” (9), Bundy exclaimed, “we’re about to take this country back by force” (14). With Bundy’s cattle secure, militia leader Mike Vanderboegh said, “it is impossible to overstate the importance of this victory won in the desert today ... courage is contagious, defiance is contagious, victory is contagious. Yet the war is not over” (9).

The war is definitely not over. Since the Battle of Bunkerville, militias have stood ground against federal agents in multiple states, have continued their paramilitary training, and have increased their border patrols.⁸³ Patriot groups and leaders from the past have seemingly awoken from hibernation, and some have already committed acts of terrorism.⁸⁴ White supremacist and neo-Nazi groups are also on the rise,⁸⁵ and—though the various right-wing groups often disagree with one another—they share a common conspiracy-theory-based, Manichean ideology that can lead to violence.

The Conspiracist Enablers

A case study in Manichean discourse would not be complete without mentioning the enablers. The conspiracism that drives extremist groups is not always a product of their

83. See Garza (2014), Lancial and Tuttle (2014), Maddow (2014a), Rosenberg (2014), Johnson (2012, Chapter 9), Thompson (2015), Toboni (2015), and Weathers (2014) for current militia activity.

84. See Gellman (2010), Holthouse (2009), Maddow (2014b), Ohlheiser and Izadi (2014), and Terry (2013) for recent acts of violence by Patriot groups and former leaders.

85. See FBI (2012), Johnson (2012), and Morlin (2011).

own creation. Sometimes they have help. As Skoll and Korstanje (2013) explained, the American fear culture stems from political and social narratives enabled by mass communication (343). Fear cultures differ from mass hysteria. Hysterias are temporary—and intense. The fear culture is subtle. It “does not require people to feel frightened all or most of the time, but it does entail patterns of behavior and a colouring [sic] of social relations grounded in a fearful outlook” (344). Americans have been bombarded for years by Manichean discourse in print, radio, television, and the Internet.

In the media, controversy sells—and so does fear. Joseph McCarthy became a celebrity by pedaling fear after claiming that communists had infiltrated the US government, and—whether he believed his own claims or not—his words fueled a wave of conspiracism-inspired paranoia that still exists today. Religious leaders and authors saturated their audiences with fear-based propaganda during the early Cold War, and the popular press repeated extremist propaganda on radio and television programs (Merkl and Weinberg 1997). Since 9/11, some politicians, media personalities, and religious leaders have made the same mistake. Professor Eric Oliver, PhD, and Thomas Wood (2014) explained that “most scholarly models prioritize elite discourse and ideological predispositions as *the* driving engine of public opinion” (953). Whether intentionally, inadvertently, or obliviously; politicians, religious leaders, and journalists have encouraged conspiracist ideation. The media—where the conspiracy meme “flourishes” Goertzel (2011)—have aided extremist recruitment by echoing its Manichean narrative. According to Professor Timothy Melley, PhD (2002), “Americans now account for all sorts of events ... through conspiracy theory. Conspiratorial explanations have become a central feature of American political discourse” (3).

In *Meet the Patriots* (2010), Southern Poverty Law Center listed nearly 20 pages of information about public figures who echo Patriot conspiracism. Personalities, such as Alex Jones, Joseph Farah, Cliff Kincaid, and Stewart Rhodes, run a host of websites that promote conspiracy theories that range from Satanists in the White House to FEMA death camps.⁸⁶ Additionally, the enablers distribute propaganda through radio, Internet, and television broadcasts as well as journals, newspapers, and magazines. Publications like *The New American*, *The Idaho Observer*, and *Soldier of Fortune Magazine* are popular Patriot sources for anti-government propaganda,⁸⁷ and religious personalities like John Hagee, Pat Robertson, and Hal Lindsey routinely use fear-based conspiracy theories in their sermons, broadcasts and literature (Coughlin 1999).

In a similar vein as the anti-communist hysteria of the early Cold War, some politicians have spread Islamophobic fears through Manichean-style discourse. Tennessee legislators introduced a bill “that would establish certain Shariah [sic] practices as *prima facie* evidence of an intent to overthrow the Constitution” (Steinback 2011). Many states have proposed “pre-emptive strikes” and “jihad prevention” bills to prevent judges from using Sharia to overrule US laws—even though US judges cannot overrule US laws (Dyson 2012, 98-111). Additionally, Michelle Bachman responded to the greenhouse gas “cap and trade” proposal by saying, “I want people in Minnesota armed and dangerous on this issue . . . we need to fight back” (SPLC 2010, 28). Fox News

86. Alex Jones is extremely popular and very well funded. He frequently promotes New World Order and anti-government conspiracy theories. He was also instrumental in rallying militia support for the Battle of Bunkerville. See www.prisonplanet.com and www.infowars.com.

87. Former US Army Special Forces Lieutenant Colonel and Vietnam veteran Robert K. Brown created *Soldier of Fortune Magazine* to “prepare Americans for the next stage of warfare” after the “failure in Vietnam” and to fight against tyranny. It is the most popular Patriot periodical with over 1 million subscribers (Atkins 2011, 207). The John Birch Society publishes *The New American*, and *The Idaho Observer* is a Patriot newspaper with the self-proclaimed mission to expose government corruption and intrusion (Mason 2006, 54–55).

supported Cliven Bundy's stand against the BLM—practically making him out to be a hero—until he made the following statement in an interview with *The New York Times* (2014):

I want to tell you one more thing I know about the Negro, ... They abort their young children, they put their young men in jail, because they never learned how to pick cotton. And I've often wondered, are they better off as slaves, picking cotton and having a family life and doing things, or are they better off under government subsidy? They didn't get no [sic] more freedom. They got less freedom. (Nagourney 2014)

The racist rant was enough for Fox News to abandon Bundy, but its initial support for the armed militia warranted constant coverage (Maddow 2014a).

The widespread conspiracy-theory-based propaganda distributed by the Patriot movement and its enablers influences individuals, groups, and governments both at home and abroad. Tamerlan Tsarnaev, one of the Boston Marathon Bombers, used al-Qaeda websites to build his bombs but found part of his justification through Patriot Movement-affiliated literature, which claimed that 9/11 and the OKC bombing were US government conspiracies (Cullison 2013). A few weeks after attending the Bunkerville standoff, Jerad and Amanda Miller left Patriot-inspired rants on social media websites before murdering federal agents who were out to lunch (SPLC 2012). Amazingly, black drug dealers in Baltimore began using *Posse Comitatus* tactics in court—even though the Posse was named after laws meant to maintain racial segregation (Cary 2008). Overseas, Al Qaeda leaders criticized Iran for spreading Patriot-style 9/11 conspiracy theories (Bartlett and Miller 2010, 19–21), and the Lebanese Foreign Ministry demanded an explanation for rumors that Hillary Clinton created the Islamic State (Taylor 2014).

Such conspiracy theory-rich environments combined with deeply held religious or Manichean worldviews create fertile breeding ground for individuals and groups to

become dangerously violent. Associate Professor Anne Aly, PhD (2012), suggested that extremist websites that do not openly promote violence use conspiracy theories for recruitment instead. By promoting conspiracist propaganda—whether intentionally or not—public figures risk aiding extremist causes. As journalist Larry Keller (2009) stated, “a remarkable aspect of the current antigovernment movement is the extent to which it has gained support from elected officials and mainstream media outlets” (8). Politicians and media personalities are not the only people who benefit from spreading fear-based conspiracist propaganda, though. Organizations do as well. Recently, the National Rifle Associated mailed solicitation letters to residents around the country. See Fig. 1 for reasons to become a member.

NATIONAL RIFLE ASSOCIATION OF AMERICA
11250 WAPLES MILL ROAD
FAIRFAX, VIRGINIA 22030
WWW.NRA.ORG

NRA

Office of the Executive Vice President
Wayne LaPierre

March 23, 2015

Dear Friend,

There has never been a more important time for you to accept the enclosed NRA membership card and carry it with pride.

Your constitutional right to own a gun is under attack by hundreds of anti-gun politicians, global gun ban diplomats at the U.N., militant anti-hunting extremists, radical billionaires and the freedom-hating Hollywood elite.

And they'll never quit... Not until they've banned and confiscated our guns, just like they did in England and Australia.

If you want to protect your guns and your precious freedoms—for you and your children—please act NOW. Please accept this card and join NRA today.

No other symbol packs the power of your NRA membership card. That's because this card has stopped hundreds of schemes to ban your guns and close down gun shows, gun shops, ranges and hunting lands.

How could this simple membership card be so powerful? Because behind this card stands the ironclad commitment of nearly five million NRA members to fight gun ban politicians and media elites who attack our guns and trample our freedoms.

This card offers crystal-clear proof to our elected leaders that if they push gun registration, licensing and prohibition, then they can expect defeat in Congress and the courts, and in the next election! It's that promise, backed by NRA membership muscle, that stops gun-banners in their tracks.

So if you believe with all your heart in the purpose and power of your NRA membership card, put it in your wallet. Then, make your personal commitment to the future of our firearm freedoms and join NRA today.

For a fraction of what it costs to buy guns, gear and ammo, you can STAND and FIGHT with NRA to defend our shooting and hunting traditions. And if you join NRA in the next 30 days, you can join at low, introductory new member rates.

That's right. If you join NRA today, you'll get a full year of NRA membership for just \$25 (normally \$35). Or you can join for three years at \$70 (normally \$85). The longer your commitment, the more you save.

Fig.1: NRA Solicitation Letter

Source: Delivered to author's address via US Postal Service

NOTE: This NRA mailer demonstrates the prevalence of conspiracy theories in American culture. Its inclusion is not an attack on the NRA or its members.

CHAPTER 4: VETERANS ON THE FRONTLINES

Even a modest study of the Patriot movement will readily uncover the prevalence of military veterans within its ranks. In fact, veterans form the “who’s who” of the Patriot movement’s groups and leaders. Many of the personalities discussed in this paper had military backgrounds, and veterans typically filled leadership positions and violent roles. Today, the trend remains as veterans take the lead in training, organizing, and mobilizing the current movements. Many authors are quick—and right—to point out that the number of veterans who join such groups is only a small percentage of those who have and continue to serve (Belew 2014; Gunter 2012; Johnson 2012). The few veterans who do become radicalized, however, are capable of bringing substantial knowledge and expertise to extremist groups.

Locked and Loaded: Military Patriots of Extremism

This chapter does not claim to be a detailed study on veteran involvement in extremist organizations. It seeks only to establish the historical—and quite significant—role veterans played within the Patriot movement. Chapter 3 discussed a number of leaders and violent members of past Patriot groups. The following (in the order they appeared in Chapter 3) were military veterans:

- Robert Shelton—US Army Air Corps and World War II veteran—became the leader of the UKA and founded One-Worldism.
- Robert DePugh—US Army—founded the paramilitary Minutemen and inspired the Militia movement.⁸⁸

⁸⁸. The Army released DePugh after one year for chronic nervousness and depression (Atkins 2011, 188).

- William Potter Gale—retired US Army Lieutenant Colonel who worked on the staff of General Douglas MacArthur and was a self-proclaimed guerrilla strategist—founded *Posse Comitatus* and fathered the Patriot movement.
- Thomas Posey—US Marine Corp—created the CMA and trafficked weapons and equipment on the black market.
- Frazier Glenn Miller—retired US Army Special Forces Vietnam veteran—founded the White Patriot Party (formerly KKK), trained KKK “Special Forces,” was a member of the Order, and murdered three people at a Jewish center in 2014.
- Louis Beam—US Army helicopter gunner and Vietnam veteran—became a KKK leader, made the FBI’s most-wanted list, and fathered the “leaderless resistance.”
- Gordon Kahl—US Army Air Corp B-25 turret gunner and World War II veteran with Silver and Bronze Stars and two Purple Hearts—became a *Posse Comitatus* “martyr” after shootouts with federal agents.
- Randy Weaver—US Army Special Forces—owned the white separatist compound at Ruby Ridge.
- James Gordon “Bo” Gritz—retired US Army Special Forces Lieutenant Colonel and Vietnam War hero—was an active Militia movement leader and propagandist.
- John Trochmann—US Navy engine mechanic—founded the Militia of Montana to fight against the New World Order.
- Richard Girnt Butler—US Army Air Corp World War II veteran—founded the Aryan Nations.
- Timothy McVeigh—US Army Gulf War veteran—became radicalized by *The Turner Dairies* and, after the incidents at Ruby Ridge and Waco, orchestrated the OKC bombing.⁸⁹
- Terry Nichols—US Army (less than one year)—was an accomplice to the OKC bombing.

The early Patriot movement was filled with veterans, many of whom supplied substantial expertise. Former Green Beret Kent Yates trained the CSA in paramilitary tactics and

89. McVeigh claimed that he received explosives training while on active duty, but Hafez and Rasmussen (2010) suggest that he did not have the ability or expertise to build such a complex device on his own. Furthermore, forensic authorities showed that McVeigh could not have constructed the device during the timeline he proposed. The bomb’s complexity and effectiveness suggest that the attack was a group effort, which required considerable expertise on multiple levels (149–50).

built weapons suppressors and improvised explosive devices. Robert Lisenby, a Vietnam veteran, and Gordon Mohr, a veteran of World War II and Korea, instructed mercenaries in the Christian Patriots Defense League. Steve Miller, a US Army Special Forces veteran and chaplain to the KKK, taught Louis Beam how to use computer networks in the early days of the Internet. Other members—both active duty and ex-military—stole weapons, equipment, ammunition, and explosives from military bases, provided financial support, created and distributed propaganda,⁹⁰ and instructed extremist groups in techniques from military tactics and survival skills to indirect fire and parachuting.⁹¹ Without veteran-supplied leadership, skills, and expertise, the Patriot movement may not have been as successful—or deadly.

Today's re-invigorated Patriot groups echo the pre-9/11 movement in many ways. After spending time with the Michigan Militia in 2002, Michaelen Kelly, PhD, and Kate Villaire said the “few” military veteran members they came across were “revered as heroes” (285). Today, veterans seem much more prominent in the Patriot movement, and recent journalism indicates that they are once again filling leadership positions. Iraq War veteran, Ryan Payne—leader of Operation Mutual Aid, an organization created to “coordinate militias across the country to respond to federal aggressions”—organized the Patriot response at Bunkerville (Lenz and Potok 2014, 11). Bundy's head of security, Booda Cavalier, is a former Marine, and members of Oath Keepers—a veteran and law enforcement only group—participated in the Bunkerville standoff (Murphy 2014; Toboni

90. The “Godmother of the Militia movement,” Linda Thompson, served in the US Army. After Waco, Thompson tried to convince the militias to overthrow the US government through letter-writing and propaganda campaigns in which she called for the arrest of Congress for treason (Atkins 2011, 224).

91. See Atkins (2011), Belew (2012), Berger (2012), Combs, Combs, and Marsh (2005), Maddow (2014b), Noble (2010), and Wright (2013) for more specifics on individuals and training within the Patriot movement.

2015). Former Army Drill Sergeant Dick Wolf travels the United States training militias (Gellman 2010), and a host of veterans instruct, organize, and lead Patriot groups across the country (Gellman 2010; Johnson 2012; Nelson 2012, Toboni 2015). Veteran militia members told journalist Gianna Toboni (2015) that they simply “want to do what’s right” and claim that the Patriots are in “every city and every town” to do so. That sounds commendable, but—like the Patriots that preceded them—they readily admit that their actions are based not on actual threats but, rather, on anti-government conspiracy theories.

Help Wanted: Targeted Recruitment

Veterans are not just leaders and trainers in extremist movements. They are also recruiters—and prized recruits. Several prominent Patriots began their journey into the world of extremism while serving in the military,⁹² and many today are following a similar path. Journalist Matt Kennard’s book, *Irregular Army* (2012), describes how extremist groups took advantage of relaxed military recruitment standards during the GWOT to obtain advanced military skills. He also claims that the US Army adopted a “don’t ask, don’t tell” policy in regard to extremism because it needed service members for the war (Chapter 1).⁹³ With or without relaxed standards, the military has a history of both former and active-duty extremist membership and recruitment. Most extremists groups are militant by nature and are likely to seek formal military training. Though the

92. Gordon Kahl, for example, became radicalized in the Army and Timothy McVeigh—though already racist—discovered *The Turner Diaries* and joined the KKK while on active duty. See Atkins (2011, 201, 238) for more details.

93. Department of Defense Instruction Number 1325.06 (2012b, 9) prohibits “actively” advocating supremacist or extremist causes (DOD 2012b is an update to the 2009 release).

DOD takes measures to mitigate extremism with its ranks,⁹⁴ some extremist activity and recruitment is still likely to take place. Many people join the military with an intense sense of patriotism, loyalty, and duty. Kelley and Villaire (2002) describe the Militia movement as providing a similar sense of honor and social status to its members. Extremist or conspiracist propaganda can sometimes turn those positive attributes toward a negative or deadly cause.

As stated in Chapter 3, veterans founded the KKK after the Civil War. Historian Kathleen Belew, PhD (2012, 2014), pointed out that its membership typically surges when veterans return from war, which proved to be the case after both World Wars and Vietnam. In 1946, half of new Klan applicants were veterans (Belew 2012, 24), and the majority of the Militia movement founders had deployed to Vietnam (Atkins 2011; Belew 2012; Wright 2013). Veterans were active in the more violent forms of the anti-communism movement and many joined extremist religious groups throughout the 1970s–1990s. Today some veterans returning from the GWOT may be following a similar pattern as they fill the ranks of militias nationwide and join racially motivated extremist groups. In 2008, the FBI reported a surge in white supremacist and neo-Nazi activity within the military. It warned that extremist groups showed signs of military training and had launched recruitment campaigns aimed at veterans. The report identified the “prestige which the extremist movement bestows upon members with military experience,” and stated that “most extremist groups have some members with military experience” who “often hold positions of authority within the groups to which they

94. Journalist Anna Mulrine (2012b) reported that former white supremacist T.J. Leyden speaks at military installations to educate service members about extremism.

belong” (5). It listed over 200 military personnel (see Fig. 2) and several organizations involved in racial extremism as well as some of the conspiracy theories they profess.

Fig.2: Military Supremacist Extremism Post-9/11

Source: FBI (2008, 5)

NOTE: Though labeled FOUO, this document is now open-source information.

Since 2008, several journalists have reported a disturbing rise in veteran radicalization,⁹⁵ and many of the Patriot and supremacist groups openly recruit veterans. In *Right-Wing Resurgence* (2012, 212–16), Daryl Johnson reported a number of Internet-based recruiting ads—spanning groups from the Nationalist Socialist Movement (NSM) to the KKK and Patriot militias—aimed specifically at veteran recruitment. The NSM claimed military “vets [coming] home from the fight” are forming new chapters. The KKK announced a new “military division” dedicated to members with military experience. The New Kentucky Militia (N.KY.) posted an advertisement for people with

95. See Elias (2012), Gunter (2012), Holthouse (2006), Keller (2009), Labi (2014), Morlin (2011), Mulrine (2012a), Neiwart (2009), SPLC (2008), and Sterman (2013).

military or law-enforcement expertise in which they exclaimed, “We need you! ... we need leaders.”

Much like the CMA of the 1980s—a group formed entirely from veterans (Belew 2012, 97)—groups like Oath Keepers are beginning to emerge. Oath Keepers became public after the 2009 DHS report leaked to the media (Johnson 2012, 4), and they swarmed to Bundy’s aid at the Battle of Bunkerville (Harmon 2015). With the motto “Not on our watch!” Oath Keepers is “an association of current and formerly serving military, police, and first responders who pledge to fulfill the oath all military and police take to ‘defend the Constitution against all enemies, foreign and domestic.’” Oath Keepers base their name on their oath to defend the Constitution, but their very existence is based on anti-government conspiracy theories. In fact, journalist Larry Keller (2009) reported that Oath Keepers were selling t-shirts that read: “I’m a Right Wing Extremist and Damn Proud of It!” (7). Their website lists 10 orders they will not obey. Eight of them are clearly based on early Patriot fears of the New World Order.⁹⁶ Oath Keepers founder and ex-US Army paratrooper Stewart Rhodes said his purpose was “to create local militia units, organized along the lines of U.S. Special Forces teams and filled with Oath Keepers, to provide security. ... ‘They can fight, of course, but they are most dangerous as a force-multiplier by helping an entire community to fight’” (SPLC 2015d). In an interview with Alex Jones he clarified what the Oath Keepers were created to fight against: “Imagine if we focus on the police and military. Game over for the New World Order” (Keller 2009, 7).

96. See the Oath Keepers website for more information at <http://oathkeepers.org/oktester/about/> (Accessed April 19, 2015). The Oath Keepers’ list of “Orders We Will Not Obey” includes direct references to concentration camps, gun confiscation, and foreign troops on US soil.

CHAPTER 5: THE POWER OF CONSPIRACISM

As soon as the infant can see, it recognizes faces, and we now know that this skill is hardwired in our brains. Those infants who a million years ago were unable to recognize a face smiled back less, were less likely to win the hearts of their parents, and less likely to prosper. These days, nearly every infant is quick to identify a human face, and to respond with a goony grin. — Astronomer Carl Sagan (Sagan 1995: 45)

Conspiracism is a complex phenomenon that results from simple processes. A number of fields—from evolutionary biology and neuroscience to the social sciences—can help to explain the ways in which humans form beliefs and worldviews. To understand how and why conspiracism so profoundly affects human psychology and behavior, one must first understand how the brain evolved to perceive the world around it—and how it makes decisions about the stimuli it receives.

The Nature of Conspiracist Ideation

In *How to Create a Human Mind* (2012), Ray Kurzweil, PhD, described the uniqueness of the human brain when he said:

We are capable of hierarchical thinking, of understanding a structure composed of diverse elements arranged in a pattern, representing that arrangement with a symbol, and then using that symbol as an element in a yet more elaborate configuration. This capability takes place in a brain structure called the neocortex, which in humans has achieved a threshold of sophistication and capacity such that we are able to call these patterns *ideas*. Through an unending recursive process we are capable of building ideas that are ever more complex. We call this vast array of recursively linked ideas *knowledge*. Only *Homo sapiens* have a knowledge base that itself evolves, grows exponentially, and is passed down from one generation to another. (2-3)

As Kurzweil explains it, the brain's main function is pattern recognition. The ability to recognize and form meaning from complex patterns is an enormously beneficial adaptive trait. It gives humans the capacity for language, mathematics, and other advanced

comprehension skills. It also comes at a price. Although the system is excellent at recognizing patterns, it does not do quite as well with logical reasoning. The brain tends to become overzealous and takes short cuts that lead to a phenomenon called *pareidolia*. Pareidolia—or false pattern recognition—is what causes people to see shapes in clouds and faces on their French toast. It is also what allows psychologists to peer into the minds of their patients using the simple inkblots of the Rorschach test (Carroll 2015b; Landford 2014). Pareidolia is—quite simply—the human brain forming patterns from random data.

Pareidolia is an everyday occurrence, and most people take it in stride. Sometimes, however, the false connections it creates can lead to an emotional response or a perception of higher meaning—like a sign from the gods or evidence for a conspiracy theory. German psychiatrist Klaus Conrad defined such a situation when he coined the term *apophänie*, which he described as the “process of repetitively and monotonously experiencing abnormal meanings” (Conrad 1959, 405 quoted in Carroll 2015a). Conrad used “apophänie” as a descriptor for symptoms of paranoid schizophrenia. Today the modern version, *apophenia*—or *cognitive pareidolia*—refers to the “perception of connections and meaningfulness of unrelated phenomena” (Carroll 2015a; Novella 2013, Chapter 19). Though apophenia is a modern term, the phenomenon is not.

Since the earliest civilizations, humans have cultivated superstitious or religious beliefs to account for patterns they could not comprehend. Natural disasters became punishments from the gods, rain dances helped water the lands, and the motions of the stars predicted the destinies of men. Carrying a rabbit’s foot became lucky, but breaking a mirror was terribly bad. Humans consistently found meaning everywhere they looked.

They also created conspiracy theories to explain the world around them. Some of the first recorded religious traditions were deeply conspiratorial. In *The Joy of Ancient History* (2014), Professor Glenn Holland, PhD, described the Mesopotamian creation myths that predate and underlie the Judeo-Christian faiths. For the Babylonians, the gods created man from the blood of a clumsy laborer and doomed him to a life of servitude. As Holland explained, these ancient myths were not concerned with *how* the creation took place, but rather *why*. They asked the *cui bono* question. The answer to that question would determine humankind's role in the world. Such religious ideas provided a framework in which nature could be understood, especially in the dualistic religions that described everything in relation to a struggle between good and evil. These ideas helped explain the reasons for why good and bad things happened to both good and bad people. They also provided a conspiratorial background for suffering, misfortune, and perceptions of unfairness: someone—or something—must have benefited from it.

In this way, conspiracism can be understood as a form of apophenia. Some conspiracy theories are based on patterns that are not actually there. Others construct false correlations between patterns and events that are unrelated. As neurologist Steven Novella, MD (2013), explained, this type of cognitive pareidolia helps people “connect the dots,” offering the “illusion of control” in the face of uncertainty (Chapter 19, 4:50). Conspiracy theories supply “the motif of cause and effect” (Kravitz 1999, 24). They also provide a narrative in which the conspiracist plays an active role. Aboriginal “cargo cults” displayed this type of apophenia in the rainforests of Papua New Guinea. After Christian missionaries began receiving supplies via airplanes at Port Moresby, the tribes created conspiracy theories to explain what they did not understand. According to

the natives, the spirits of their ancestors were attempting to send supplies from the heavens, but the devious foreigners had snared them in an airport trap. In hopes of defeating the white man's magic, the indigenous people constructed mock airports at the tops of mountains. There they patiently waited, praying for their spiritual supplies to arrive (*Mondo Cane* 1963).⁹⁷

The cargo cults demonstrate how conspiracism can profoundly affect behavior. Much like religion, it can become a framework in which the conspiracist understands the world. Conspiracy theories are stories that explain apophenia, and stories are an important part of human culture (Raab et al. 2013, 8). When conspiracists tell such stories they often ascribe “supernormal agency” to conspirators, and—like religions—conspiracy theories represent external agents as omniscient and omnipotent (Bradley, Bangerter, and Bauer 2013, 9). Oliver and Wood (2014) suggest that the strongest predictors of conspiracist ideation are: “a propensity to attribute the source of unexplained or extraordinary events to unseen, intentional forces” and “a natural attraction toward melodramatic narratives as explanations for prominent events, particularly those that interpret history relative to universal struggles between good and evil” (954). These predictors largely describe the nature of many religious beliefs—as well as the plots of fairytales, mystery novels, and science fiction films. They are, perhaps, integral parts of the human imagination.

In a lecture on the possible cognitive reasons for superstitious and religious beliefs, psychiatrist Anderson Thomson, MD (2009), described such belief as a “by-product of cognitive mechanisms designed for other purposes” that arises “as an artifact

97. *Mondo Cane* (1963) is a “shockumentary” that consists of both archival footage and staged rituals; see <http://www.imdb.com/title/tt0057318/>. “Cargo cults” like the one described in *Mondo Cane* are not exclusive to Papua New Guinea and have been reported since the late 19th century (Dalton 2000).

of our ability to imagine social worlds” (8:30). Professor David Sloan Wilson, PhD (2003), presented religion as a sort of biological adaptation that serves a functional, social role in human group selection. Biologist Richard Dawkins, PhD (2006), and Philosopher Daniel Dennett, PhD (2002), described the idea that memes—or cultural ideas—propagate and evolve in social environments much like genes do in biological systems. All of these ideas apply to conspiracism. Conspiracy theories can stem from a number of cognitive traps (Novella 2013, Chapter 19), and they can also lead to habitual ways of thinking (Goertzel 2011). The “conspiracist worldview implies a universe governed by design rather than by randomness” (Barkun 2003, 3). It provides the conspiracist—or storyteller—with a narrative that attracts people, allowing them to fill “logical gaps” with their “own considerations” (Raab et al., 2013). The conspiracist becomes part of a privileged and enlightened few (Novella 2013), whose ideas are “easy to propagate and difficult to refute ... When an alleged fact is debunked, the conspiracy meme often just replaces it with another fact” (Goertzel 2011). Professor Michael Barkun, PhD (2003), compares conspiracy theories to urban legend-like folklore. They are more believable than fairytales but circulate through the Internet and mass media with almost religious-like authority (12–14).

From a social constructivist perspective—and given a definition of conspiracy theory as a form of apophenia—conspiracism becomes a natural means for self-identification in response to the social, political, and mythical environments.⁹⁸ It is no longer reserved for the delusional or paranoid. It becomes rational. It is simply a best attempt to understand complex problems using whatever information is available (Barkun

98. Social constructivism in International Relations theory argues that “human reality is socially constructed,” meaning that individuals form their self-identities through engagement with the social world into which they are born (Peoples and Vaughan-Williams 2015, 16).

2003; Novella 2013, Chapter 19; Sunstein and Vermuele 2009; Swami et al. 2011, 444).

That does not mean conspiracism is a benign phenomenon, however. Nor does it suggest that conspiracism will inevitably lead to extreme behavior. Like all belief systems, it will produce a range of believers from dabblers to fanatics. Conspiracism alone can push people toward extremist behavior, but it can also complement other reasons for extremist beliefs. When either of these situations occur, and conspiracism becomes part of a Manichean ideology, it can become deadly.

Conspiracism and the Extremist Mentality

According to Oliver and Wood (2014, 953), “Americans periodically have organized themselves around narratives about hidden, malevolent groups secretly perpetuating political plots and social calamities to further their own nefarious goals.”⁹⁹ These kinds of narratives are attractive because they provide “compelling explanations for confusing, ambiguous events” (954). When such events happen, people tend toward emotional explanations that can simultaneously rationalize the occurrence and relieve emotional stress associated with it (Sunstein and Vermuele 2009, 213). Most people do not like to believe in luck or chance, so they find evidence for intentionality (208). The apophenia-induced conspiracy theory that results reinforces Manichean perspectives and monological thinking—both of which lead to and are products of conspiracism (Oliver and Wood 2014). Monological thinkers tend to view everything they experience as evidence for a single narrative. New events become inherently conspiratorial and new

99. The American propensity to accept such conspiracy theories is only one example. Räikkä (2009, 187) points out that similar cases are common throughout human history. See Aaronovitch (2010) and Hodapp and Van Konnon (2008) for more examples.

conspiracy theories become additional evidence for conspiracism.¹⁰⁰ When conspiracism fuels monological belief systems that contain Manichean worldviews, the resultant feedback loop can produce dangerous results.

The Patriot movement serves as an exceptional case study for conspiracism-based extremism because most of the Patriot groups demonstrated some, if not all, of the predictors for conspiracism. Oliver and Wood (2014) found that people with a belief in religious eschatology or those with a Manichean perspective on history are most likely to accept conspiracy theories (961). People who believe in the supernatural or paranormal also tend toward conspiracism (953). Many of the Patriots were Christian millennialists—people who believe they are living in the end times—and much of their propaganda, from the beginning of the Cold War to the present, has been apocalyptic in nature (Barkun 2003; Coughlin 1999; Learned 2012).¹⁰¹ Professor Jonathan White, PhD (2001), pointed out that radical religious leaders “provided the theological underpinnings” of right-wing extremists after World War II, and Barkun (2003) explained that “prior to the 1990s, New World Order conspiracism was limited to ... the militant antigovernment right” and “Christian fundamentalists concerned with the end-time emergence of the Antichrist” (179). The New World Order became an agent of evil and Christian fundamentalists produced a massive amount of end-times and New World Order propaganda through cable television, magazines, and books—but it was meant for a niche audience. In the early days of the Internet, however, the New World Order conspiracy theories became popular in other circles as Patriot groups and Christian millennialists presented them to

100. See Goertzel (1994) and Thresher-Andrews (2013) for more details about monological belief systems.

101. Eschatological beliefs are not exclusive to religions. Barkun (2003) pointed out that Marxism, Nazism, and various forms of nationalism became secular millennialist movements with symbolic battles between good and evil (16–18).

wider audiences. Similarly, the Internet exposed the Patriots to new types of conspiracy theories, such as those based in ufology and alien cover-ups. Unsurprisingly, many groups incorporated the new ideas into their narratives (179–81).¹⁰²

Patriot Manichean perspectives on the end of history, coupled with the “hidden hand” of the global order, fueled the survivalist and militia movements, which brought with them the Patriots’ “greatest military potential” (White 2001, 944).¹⁰³ In the early days of the Cold War, groups like the John Birch Society—and even the KKK—were somewhat prominent public actors. As the Patriots trained in military tactics, stockpiled weapons, and shared conspiracy theories with one another, they moved closer to insurgent-type behavior. Conspiracists become less inclined to engage in politics although they usually develop an intense desire for their opinions to be heard (Lantian 2013, 20; Thresher-Andrews 2013, 6). They develop the *sinister attribution error*, which produces the perception that “benign actions that [just so] happen to disadvantage the group” are part of the conspiratorial plot. The sinister attribution error causes groups and individuals to become more distrustful and suspicious. This leads to the *cascade effect*, which turns non-believers into part of the conspiracy (Sunstein and Vermeule 2009).¹⁰⁴ The conspiracist starts to view people who fail to discover, believe, or reveal the conspiracy as complicit to it (Goertzel 2011). As the conspiracy becomes ever-more

102. Timothy McVeigh was a UFO enthusiast and visited Area 51 less than a year before the OKC bombing. McVeigh was an avid listener to shortwave radio broadcasts by Milton William Cooper—a popular conspiracist who believed that the government was involved in a plot with extraterrestrials (Barkun 2003, ix).

103. In “Hermetic Histories: Divine Providence and Conspiracy Theory” (2007, 174), Brian Bennett suggested “providentialism looks for the ‘hand of God’ in historical events” while “conspiracism is concerned not with the ‘hand of God’ but [rather with] the ‘hidden hand.’”

104. Sunstein and Vermeule (2009, 217) noted that the sinister attribution error resembles “individual-level pathologies” but is actually a product of the “social and informational structure of the group.” They also pointed out that the cascade effect can cause conspiracists to expect others to share their beliefs (213–14).

pervasive, *agency panic*—an “intense anxiety about an apparent loss of autonomy or self-control”—sets in, causing the conspiracist to believe that the world is full of “brainwashed” people (Melley 2002, 62–63).¹⁰⁵

With the world controlled by nefarious and powerful ruling elites, extremists begin to see themselves as part of vanguard party. Vanguardist groups believe that they represent the masses, which have been enslaved by the government, the media, or an oppressive education system. The “people cannot see the real ‘truth’” of their indoctrination (Bartlett and Miller 2010, 31). According to researchers Jamie Bartlett and Carl Miller (2010, 30), “vanguardism has been one of the most consistent attributes of violent extremist groups over the last century.” From Leninists to Patriots to al Qaeda operatives, vanguardist-extremist groups emphasize a small cadre of revolutionaries who must act on behalf of all others. Conspiracy theories create a sense of urgency, and conspiracism leaves the vanguardists with no other options—at least in their minds.

Terrorism expert Adam Dolnik, PhD, (2008), explained that terrorists range from the mentally ill to the highly intelligent. Furthermore, most terrorists fit the typical profile of military personnel and law enforcement officers. They are action-oriented people who are willing to use violence if necessary. Contrary to conventional wisdom, terrorism is not simply a product of insanity or paranoia. According to Dolnik, most terrorists view their actions as a last resort, and there is an “altruistic motive involved.” In the terrorists’ minds, they have been attacked therefore they “go and fight—and punish” (28:25–29:05). Timothy McVeigh recreated a scene from *The Turner Diaries* when he killed over 150 people in Oklahoma City. He built the bomb to the specifications described in the book,

105. Popular conspiracy theory proponents like Alex Jones frequently use the term “sheeple”—a combination of sheep and people—to describe people who obviously go about their everyday lives like sheep following the herd.

and he did so in response to Waco (Brister and Kollars 2011, 59; CJES 2010, 19–20; Cronin 2011, 79). Similarly, Robert Mathews created the Order based on a deadly organization from the same conspiracy-theory-based story. His motivation was the destruction of the Zionist Occupied Government (Atkins 2011, 156–57). Fueled by conspiracism, both terrorists sought to create a revolution through vanguardism. Both would die trying (Belew 2012, 253; Stanley 2010).

Bartlett and Miller (2010) described conspiracism as a “‘radicalizing multiplier,’ which feeds back into the ideologies, internal dynamics and psychological processes” of extremist groups. It holds such “groups together and push[es] them in a more extreme and sometimes violent direction” (4–5). Manichean narratives demonize and dehumanize “outsiders” (30–35), creating an “objectification of evil” that manifests in “others.” According to Sigmund Freud, individuals and groups tend to aggregate their own negative character traits—their “dark side”—and project them onto opposing individuals and groups (Buehler 2011, 646). This process has been shown to be a natural product of human psychology. The brain evolved to understand relationships through a tribal mentality and adopted an automatic fear response towards unfamiliar individuals and groups. Biologist Edward O. Wilson, PhD, explained the process in *The Social Conquest of Earth* (2012, Chapter 7). He described how studies have shown that the amygdala—the fear center of the brain, which plays a role in memory, decision-making, and emotional responses—reacts to unfamiliar or stereotypical individuals. The fear response is immediate and unconscious, but it can be overridden by contextual cues. In other words, humans can learn to trust individuals who are different and bring them into the group or tribe. People can also be taught to fear and hate by association.

Both fear of the “other” and conspiracism can lead to vanguardism, and extremist groups already tend to fall victim to *group polarization*. Sunstein and Vermeule (2009) describe group polarization as a phenomenon in which “members of a deliberating group typically end up in a more extreme position” than before the deliberation began (216).¹⁰⁶ The extremism of the whole is greater than the sum of its parts. Conspiracy theories tend to discredit criticism, demonize the “others,” and potentially justify violence, leading to the formation of groups of likeminded people. Group polarization increases the likelihood that those people will become radicalized or violent and reinforces the Manichean perspective. Group polarization also fuels conspiracism (Sunstein and Vermeule 2009, 216)—which itself can lead to Manichean worldviews. Conspiracism exaggerates vanguardism, and vanguardism substantially increases the potential for terrorism. It is a feedback loop of epic proportions. A simple perception of intentionality, based on apophenia-induced conspiracy theories, can lead to a world of complexity that demands violent action.

The Conspiracist Pidgin: Crossing the Ideological Spectrum

When groups that speak different languages inhabit the same area, they will likely need to work together towards some common goals. Slaves from different tribes with different languages, for example, sometimes found themselves working on the same plantations. Out of necessity, they created new forms of communication. These types of collaborations produce “pidgin” languages, which are “fragmentary” communication systems that are “made up of bits and pieces” of “relevant languages” that groups use to

106. Additionally, George and Wilcox (1992, 58) stressed the tendency for extremists to “identify themselves in terms of who their enemies are.” This can lead to an emotional bond with and emulation of their opponents—meaning groups develop negative emotional attachments to rival groups and become more violent in response to the real or perceived tactics their rivals use against them.

understand each other (Sapolsky 2010b, 9:31). In a similar fashion, divergent extremist groups sometimes find themselves working toward mutual goals or against common enemies. Though their methods, ideologies, and interests may drastically differ, conspiracy theories can become the conspiracist pidgin that allows extremist groups to break through the communication barrier.

Uscinski, Parent, and Torres (2011) found that during times of low external threat, groups tend to conspire against each other. During times of high external threat, however, “foreigner-fearing conspiracy theories” come “to the fore” (5). The Patriots demonstrated this trend on several occasions when somewhat oppositional groups joined forces in response to what they believed was ZOG tyranny. Terrorism experts Gary Ackerman, PhD, and Jeffery Bale, PhD, presented similar data in “The Potential for Collaboration between Islamist and Western Left-wing Extremists” (2012). Though they found no significant cases of operational collaborations, Ackerman and Bale identified 22 instances of cooperative political mobilization or logistical support from 1980–2008. According to the report, the chief reason for cross-ideological collaboration between Islamist and Western leftists is a mutual hatred for the New World Order, American imperialism, and the state of Israel (151).

The Anti-Defamation League (2003) reported that 9/11 conspiracies “have united disparate groups of Jew haters—American far-right extremists, white supremacists and elements within the Arab and Muslim world—who are exchanging and echoing information, ideas, and conspiracy theories, particularly through the Internet.” Brister and Kollars (2011) explained that right-wing extremist groups have sought collaboration with Islamic Jihadists who lack access to targets within the United States. Because the two

groups share an intense hatred for the ZOG, some Patriots have offered to help Jihadists gain entry into the United States. In fact, the Aryan Nations has already established a Ministry of Islamic Liaison (63–65).¹⁰⁷

Bartlett and Miller (2010) found conspiracism prevalent among over 50 extremist groups across the ideological spectrum. All of the groups had been active within the past 30 years (3).¹⁰⁸ The most commonly held belief was some variant of the ZOG conspiracy theory, which claims that Jewish elites secretly control the world (22). The mutual belief provides a potential reason for groups to put aside their differences—at least temporarily—and “go and fight” together. During the Red Scares several religious groups came together against the “atheistic enemy of religion.” Communists and religious leaders united against the “imperialists” and the Nazis. Patriots from across the right-wing spectrum reached a mutual agreement at the Rocky Mountain Rendezvous, and several groups rallied together at the Battle of Bunkerville. As Paul Brister (2010) explained, the only thing that holds together the diverse leaderless resistance groups of the Patriot movement is a common set of conspiracy theories and a hatred for the New World Order (185). A similar situation seems to be emerging on the global extremist stage. Islamic extremist and Jihadist groups have come together against the West, and Patriots, Jihadists, and leftists have all shown some degree of willingness to collaborate to certain degrees. These groups have a common enemy, a common goal, and the beginnings of a common language. The conspiracist pidgin may be taking shape.

107. In 2005, Aryan Nations leader August Kreis, publicly called for an alliance with al Qaeda to fight their mutual enemies—Jews and the American government. Kreis does not believe that al Qaeda perpetrated the attacks on 9/11 (Schuster 2005). Additionally, National Anarchists and al-Qaeda members have already collaborated based on shared conspiracy theories, and European left-wing terrorists have conducted training at Palestine Liberation Organization (PLO) training camps (Bartlett and Miller 2010, 5).

108. Some groups, such as the Real IRA, did not profess beliefs in conspiracy theories (4).

CHAPTER 6: COMBATING CONSPIRACISM

According to leading critical-thinking educators Linder Elder, PhD, and Richard Paul, PhD (2008b, 3), “humans live in a world of thoughts ... but the thoughts we perceive as true are sometimes false, unsound, or misleading.” In today’s world, people are bombarded by information. From education-based websites like *Khan Academy* to viral advertising and the anything-goes blogosphere, the Internet offers unprecedented access to knowledge—and propaganda. Research suggests that this mass consumption of information is “affecting our capacity for ‘deep-processing’ skills: inductive analysis, critical thinking, imagination, and reflection.” It also indicates that young people are not developing the “personal critical abilities to discriminate between truth and its many imposters” (Bartlett and Miller 2010, 37). On the other hand, however, Professor James Flynn, PhD (2013), explained that overall intelligence quotient (IQ) test scores are increasing. The higher IQ scores are a result of our increasing capability for abstraction. People are getting better at “connecting the dots.” Sometimes, however, there are no dots to connect.

Conspiracy theories are no longer reserved for niche or fringe groups (Raab et al. 2013). Professor Mark Fenster, PhD (2008, 1), called cyberspace the “petri dish for paranoids.” He also said conspiracy theories permeate movies, television, books, and video games. Now they are prevalent around the globe.¹⁰⁹ In America, conspiracy theories often combine with fear in popular literature and the media. Their number has

109. See Banas and Miller (2013), Bartlett and Miller (2010), and Sunstein and Vermeule (2009, 202).

also steadily increased since World War II.¹¹⁰ Books about an impending doomsday, such as Y2K or the Mayan Apocalypse, maintain a healthy level of fear.¹¹¹ Movies such as *The Da Vinci Code* (2006), *The Bourne Identity* (2002), and *National Treasure* (2004) suggest an ever-present “hidden hand.” Television shows like *Ancient Aliens* (2009–), *The X-Files* (1993–2002), and *Conspiracy Theory with Jesse Ventura* (2009–) tell us to “trust no one.” For most people, this is simply entertainment. For others, much of it is real. For everyone, it is data.

Intuition and Reason

The human brain uses two systems of thinking, which author Daniel Gardner explains in *The Science of Fear* (2008). System one is subconscious. It is fast, emotional, and instinctual. System two is slower and more methodical, calculating, and considerate. Gardner calls system one “Gut” or “Feeling.” System two is “Head” or “Reason” (15, 26). Both Gut and Head are survival adaptations that rely heavily on pattern recognition. Gut reacts in an instant to any sign of immediate danger or time-sensitive gain. Head, however, takes its time to analyze its environment, reflecting, rationalizing, and planning with logic and reasoning skills. The systems work “semi-independently of each other” with “constant, complex interaction between the two” (27). Gut’s “snap judgments”—

110. See Barkun (2003), Cimino (2005), Kravitz (1999), Melley (2002), and Skoll and Korstanje (2013).

111. Y2K proponents believed that the year 2000—hence the name Y2K—would bring with it an economic collapse. A technical error in computer programming threatened to crash systems when the date changed from 1999 to 2000 because the programs would misinterpret the new date as 1900. Y2K became a bringer-of-the-apocalypse in some Christian communities (Coughlin 1999, 15–16), and many Patriot groups believed it would be the catalyst that would enable the New World Order to take full control of the United States (Domingue 2001; Keller 2009, 8; SPLC 2010). Similarly, the year 2012 replaced 2000 as the new beginning of the apocalypse after Y2K passed without a hitch. This time people believed that the end of the Mayan calendar—technically the rollover of the Mayan calendar—predicted the end of the world. Like Y2K, some Christians linked the new doomsday prediction to the biblical Book of Revelation, and conspiracists incorporated it into New World Order plots to take over the United States (Barkun 2003).

which we experience as hunches, intuition, and feelings of “unease, worry or fear”—can be “hard or even impossible to explain in words” (16). Head’s rationalizations can lead to overconfidence when caution should be preferred. The two often compete with one another. Head tries to keep Gut in check while Gut constantly attempts to persuade Head. As Ray Kurzweil (2014, 3:48–3:55) put it, “your brain create[s] your thoughts, and ... your thoughts create your brain.”

Gardner (2008, 16) called the system “brilliant”—but also lazy. It relies on a number of heuristics—or rules of thumb—that can produce a variety of cognitive errors. The *appearance-equals-reality rule*, for example, convinces the brain that anything that walks like a duck and quacks like a duck must actually be a duck (25). The *Von Restorff Effect* describes a “bias in favor of remembering the unusual” (28), but—because of the *availability heuristic*—the brain tends to determine the probability of something being true based on how easily it can recall similar examples (15–16). Additionally, *confirmation bias* leads us to readily accept new evidence when it conforms to our preconceived notions, while evidence to the contrary gets rejected or ignored (Hodapp and Von Kannon 2008, 24). These and other cognitive errors cause the brain to make decisions based on “scant evidence” (Gardner 2008, 29). In the words of Nobel-Prize winning psychologist Daniel Kahneman, PhD, “people are not accustomed to thinking hard and are often content to trust a plausible judgment that comes quickly to mind” (Schrage 2003, 1).

Making quick decisions does not always lead to error. In fact, Gut’s reactions quite often result in great success. Psychologist Gary Klein, PhD (1999), studied the quick decision-making skills of firefighters, military personnel, and nurses to explain the

power of intuition (Chapter 4). When navigating complex, challenging, and dangerous situations, they often acted effectively but in ways they could not consciously understand. One firefighter, for example, was convinced that he possessed extra-sensory perception because he made decisions in response to situations of which he was not fully aware (32–35). This “sixth sense,” however, proved to be simply the product of skilled intuition.

According to Klein:

Intuition depends on the use of experience to recognize key patterns that indicate the dynamics of the situation. Because patterns can be subtle, people cannot describe what they noticed, or how they judged a situation as typical or atypical. Therefore, intuition has a strange reputation. Skilled decision-makers know that they can depend on their intuition, but at the same time they may feel uncomfortable trusting a source of power that seems so accidental. (31)

Professional athletes, soldiers, paramedics, and others who must think fast and act quickly are successful because of muscle memory powered by trained intuition. Head can teach Gut to make better instinctual decisions (Banas and Miller 2013; Gardner 2008; Klein 1999) Without that training or experience however, intuition can produce quite different results.

Conspiracism is largely a product of flawed intuition. It has the same power of Klein’s trained intuition, but it works in the opposite direction. Conspiracy theories present information in a way that “feels right” (Banas and Miller 2013, 187), strengthening the potential for false pattern recognition. Conspiracism is not just a product of apophenia—it also encourages it. Novella (2013, Chapter 19, 25:40–25:50) explained that conspiracy theories “meet many psychological needs,” are “built on cognitive biases,” and are “maintained with logical fallacies.” According to Professor John Banas, PhD, and Gregory Miller (2013, 187), “conspiratorial arguments often employ circular reasoning ... and a host of logical flaws.” Conspiracy theories create a

closed belief system that immunizes itself to refutation, shifts the burden of proof to its challengers, and squeezes reality into preconceived notions of what “should happen” (Novella 2013, Chapter 19, 10:10–16:30). Simply speaking, they appeal to Gut in such a way to convince Head that it should follow along.

Conspiracism turns refutation into circumstantial evidence. Its ability to self-insulate makes it difficult to combat (Brotherton 2013, 9; Sunstein and Vermeule 2009, 210). The more intense the belief, the harder it is to dislodge (Elder and Paul 2008a), and countering with “authoritative information is likely to be counterproductive” (Uscinski, Parent, and Torres 2011, 33). “Simply exposing people to more information doesn’t help” either (Aschwanden 2015). Conspiracists should not be told *what* to think. They must be taught *how* to think. As philosopher Charles Pigden, PhD (2007, 220), put it, “we cannot decide what to believe or disbelieve ... we are moved by the evidence or we are not.”

Constructing a Framework

“But just because we cannot *always* choose to believe, it does not follow that we can *never* choose to believe” (Pigden 2007, 220). Perhaps conspiracists can choose *not* to believe if Head possesses the right tools to reject Gut’s persuasion. Given the proper framework and ways to think critically, the false patterns that support conspiracy theories may dissolve. Apophenia emerges from self-deception, but it is also contagious. Mere exposure to conspiracy theories can make people more prone to believing them.¹¹²

Combating conspiracism requires “a system for intellectual intervention, a method for pre-empting bad thinking.” Conspiracists must “take rational control of [their] cognitive

112. See Bartlett and Miller (2010, 35), Jolley (2013, 35), Lemman and Cinnirella (2013, 7), Oliver and Wood (2014, 956), and Swami et al. (2011).

processes in order to rationally determine what to accept and what to reject” (Elder and Paul 2008b, 3).

It is important to note, however, that conspiracy theories should not be rejected out of hand. A conspiracy theory is simply “a way of looking at a single event and postulating” that there may be “a lot more to it than can be seen on the surface” (Hodapp and Von Kannon 2008, 10). Many scholars have pointed out that conspiracy theories are not inherently irrational,¹¹³ nor do they inevitably lead to conspiracism. Sometimes, conspiracy theories provide the only rational or viable explanation for an event (Dentith 2014). Conspiracies have taken place in the past, and they will happen in the future.¹¹⁴ Philosopher Lee Basham, PhD (2001, 275), said conspiracy theories confront “us with a new creativity and challenging broadness in our conception of the real range of possibilities—a refreshing tendency to ‘think outside of the box.’” Conspiracy theories can actually be useful tools for challenging and honing our critical thinking skills. They can also expose corruption and help to keep power in check. Conspiracy theories *per se* are not necessarily dangerous, but the ones that rely on fallacious reasoning, bad evidence, and biased conclusions definitely can be. Those are the types that push believers toward conspiracism, because conspiracism employs the same flaws in thinking. Conspiracy theories can sometimes offer a dose of healthy skepticism, but conspiracism may lead to vanguardist extremes.

113. See Basham (2001), Dentith (2012, 2014), Novella (2013), Pigden (2007), Raab et al. (2013), and Rääkkä (2009).

114. In the case of 9/11, for example, a conspiracy theory explains the attacks regardless of whether they were a product of al Qaeda operatives, a machination of the ZOG, or a false-flag by the US government (Dentith 2014; Novella 2013). The term “false flag” is a synonym for “inside job.” It derives from the fact that naval ships (and pirate ships) carried flags from several countries so they could “tactically hide their identity if necessary” (Hodapp and Von Kannon 2008, 137).

Conspiracy theories are built on cognitive errors. They employ fallacious reasoning, which is a defense mechanism that “distorts reality” in such a way to present an appearance of logic, objectivity, and reasonability (Elder and Paul 2008a, 6). By definition, fallacies are deceptive and manipulative. As “self-deceiving animals,” humans are vulnerable to such trickery (3). Conspiracy theories cite “the existence of a conspiracy as a salient cause” (Dentith 2012, 6), but they are based on “weak kinds of evidence” (Brotherton 2013, 9). They frequently depend on particular interpretations of “half-hidden clues, telltale signs, and secret messages” (Melley 2002, 66). They use negative argumentation to cause doubt about pre-existent beliefs and turn that doubt into a type of new evidence that does not actually exist (Dentith 2014). Conspiracy theories also encourage believers to jump to conclusions, forming false connections in response to vague argumentation (Lantian 2013, 31). Ultimately, the ambiguous evidence leads the conspiracist to rely on confirmation heuristics (Leman and Cinnirella 2013, 2). In the end, Gut beats Head because Head cannot disagree.

Several factors contribute to conspiracist ideation: anomie, powerlessness, alienation, monological thinking, low self-esteem, and lack of trust are just some examples (Bartlett and Miller 2010; Goertzel 1994; Thresher-Andrews 2013). Conspiracy theories offer psychological comfort and give the conspiracist a vested interest in the story.¹¹⁵ People may be prone to conspiracism because they sense a lack of control (Swami et al. 2011, 459), have a desire to feel significant, or possess a flawed “theory of

115. Banas and Miller (2013, 186) explained that conspiracy theories provide psychological comfort by allowing the conspiracist to take on the role of the victim, by self-purification through scapegoating, or by offering the “thrill” of “secret information.” Leman and Cinnirella (2013, 2) demonstrated that the need for cognitive closure (NFCC)—or vested interest—causes people to rely on confirmation heuristics when making decisions about whether or not to believe conspiracy theories. People with NFCC more readily accept conspiracy theories as valid explanations.

power that fails to recognize real power relations in modern society” (Fenster 1999, 67 quoted in Mason 2006, 171). Elder and Paul (2008a, 3) suggested that social conditioning or indoctrination has created “unreflexive thinkers,” meaning:

“They are focused on what immediately affects them. ... When their beliefs are threatened—however unjustified those beliefs may be—they feel personally attacked. ... They want to be told who is evil and who is good. They see themselves as “good.” They see their enemies as “evil.” ... The mass media are structured to appeal to such persons. Spin is everything; substance is irrelevant. (3–4)

Some people simply fall victim to propagandists who are “skilled in the art of manipulation and control” (6).

Education is essential to combating conspiracism.¹¹⁶ People must learn to think critically and be able to both identify and navigate fallacious arguments—but to be effective, critical thinking requires a firm intellectual framework. One cannot reason without data to inform it. As Sunstein and Vermeule (2009) pointed out, people fall victim to conspiracy theories due to a “crippled epistemology.” They cannot reason with what they do not know, and conspiracism may seem justified in relation to limited information. Most modern conspiracy theories are based on common misperceptions or purposeful misrepresentations of global institutions, economics, historical events, and matters of politics. If a person lacks critical-thinking skills or is unfamiliar with the power of logical fallacies, he is at a disadvantage when confronted with conspiracist propaganda. If he lacks at least basic knowledge in subjects such as government administration, economics, history, and political science, he is almost certainly doomed.

For her PhD dissertation, “Insurgency on the Populist Right” (2006), Lorna Mason completed a case study on Patriot ideology. She spent substantial time with

116. Several scholars have pointed out a negative correlation between belief in conspiracy theories and education levels (Oliver and Wood 2014; Shermer 2014; White 2001).

members of a Patriot group and conducted extensive interviews and research. She found the Patriots to be heavily influenced by general misunderstandings of economic and political realities—and by conspiracy theories. The Patriots rely on propagandists, such as the John Birch Society and popular New World Order conspiracist Devvy Kidd, for the bulk of their “information.” Mason said the Patriots “use conspiracy theory to point to real economic and political conditions as a means of explaining real inequalities in power” (171). The Patriots commonly justified their beliefs based on conspiracy theories about the Federal Reserve (FED), the World Trade Organization (WTO), the United Nations (UN), INTERPOL, and a number of other institutions, as well as income taxes, the gold standard, and communism (150–69). These types of narratives can undermine confidence in democratic institutions and end up fueling conspiracism (Banas and Miller 2013, 184). If a conspiracist does not understand, for example, how or why the FED or the UN exist and operate—or the historical processes by which they were created—basic critical-thinking skills may not be enough to prevent him from believing that the FED or the UN are part of the New World Order.¹¹⁷ If it looks like the New World Order and sounds like the New World Order—without a framework with which to analyze the parts of the New World Order—it *is* the New World Order.

Education as a Weapon

One cannot “think outside of the box” if she cannot first think within it—or if she does not know what the box actually is. The Covenant, Sword, and Arm of the Lord (CSA) founder Kerry Noble (2010) did not turn from extremism because someone told him that his beliefs were wrong. He had to learn that for himself, and the knowledge came from

117. Keller (2000, 9) calls the Federal Reserve a “long-time bogeyman of the radical right.”

experience. He defeated conspiracism by acquiring new data. He updated his framework.

According to Noble:

The first key in dealing with the right-wing is to make them re-examine their beliefs (284). What individuals believe determines what they do. And those who are in authority in the movement are making sure that the followers feel cornered to force them into action. Therefore if you can change the belief system and the basic premise of the individuals, you can begin to stop an entire movement. (278)

In *Tabernacle of Hate* (2010), Noble described his first-hand experience as a right-wing extremist. He belonged to one of the most radical Patriot groups of the 1990s. Its members were the first to plan an attack on the Alfred P. Murrah building in Oklahoma City. The CSA began as a religious cult with the original intent to give up modernity and live modestly in accordance with their faith. Their goals changed drastically after a conspiracist—former Army soldier John Todd—introduced Noble and the others to the New World Order (75). As Noble described it, the conspiracy theories confirmed all that they had “felt was wrong in this country, as well as what [they] believed would happen in the future “ (77). The New World Order meant the “imminent collapse of our nation, perpetrated by our own leaders” (81). The CSA responded to the conspiracy-theory-based threat by stockpiling weapons and training with explosives in preparation for a “war against the government” (159), and former Army Green Beret, Kent Yates, began planning their preemptive attack (158–72).

According to Professor Bennett Kravitz, PhD (1999), America “has been fascinated with the idea of conspiracy as a fact of life both on the private and public levels since the conclusion of World War II ... Since the 1960s, every generation of Americans has grown up on conspiracy theories” (23). Today, Americans demonstrate a high familiarity with and vulnerability to the conspiracist mentality. Furthermore, they

show a high agreement with Manichean perspectives on history (Oliver and Wood 2014). According to a number of opinion polls, over 1/3 of Americans consider it “very likely” or “somewhat likely” that the US government was involved in—whether by allowing or actually carrying out—the attacks on 9/11 (Bartlett and Miller 2010, 18).

Laura Lanford (2014) explained that the human mind can be primed for pareidolia. When the brain receives a suggestion about what to expect, false patterns will more readily emerge. Many Americans are already primed for conspiracism. “A kind of paranoia” has settled over many groups—and they depend on it for their survival (Melley 2009, 57). Conspiracism concentrates on “sources of anger” (Vertigans 2007, 645). It uses ideas and images from folklore and religions to elicit an emotional response (Barkun 2003), and it simplifies complexity, making irrational decisions seem like good ideas (Novella 2013; White 2001). Swami et al. (2011) suggested, however, that “conspiracist ideation begins as an individual decision-making process” (459). Under the right conditions, inoculation messages can be “effective in conferring resistance to persuasion” (Banas and Miller 2013, 187). As Banas and Miller (2013, 186) explained, “inoculation theory proposes that individuals can be inoculated against counter-attitudinal attacks in a manner similar to immunization against viral attacks.” Inoculation is education. Effective inoculation against conspiracism is education with critical thinking, logic, and reason. It must foster critical thinking and educate people on the nature of fallacious reasoning, but it must also provide an adequate framework in which effective critical thinking, logic, and reasoning can occur.

An Avenue for Application: US Army Education

As demonstrated throughout this paper, the US Army—and America at large—has a long history of conspiracism-based extremism. Many of the most violent members and leaders of the Patriot movement had substantial military experience. Others served for shorter tours of duty, but the entire movement benefited from veteran training and leadership. Today, potentially violent groups are becoming increasingly active, and many target military members for recruitment. With a history of conspiracist veterans and a drive for a better-educated force, the Army is in a unique position to apply an education-based approach for combating conspiracism and, consequently, the extremism it can lead to.

When he addressed students of the Sergeants Major Course in 2013, former Sergeant Major of the Army (SMA) Raymond Chandler III said, “Sergeants Major will be expected to use their influence and critical thinking skills more effectively and efficiently ... NCO education is going to shape the Army’s future” (Portillo 2013). More recently, the newest SMA, Dan Daily, said, “we need to raise academic standards” because “analysis says we can” and “it will make [the Army] a better force” (Tice 2015a). The Army has, in fact, been emphasizing education since the end of the Cold War (DA 2008, 2), and it is currently improving its Professional Military Education (PME) systems—especially for noncommissioned officers (NCO). As it works to better-educate the force, the Army is developing new programs, such as “broadening” seminars that bring Army officers, NCOs, and academics together to discuss strategic security issues (Tice 2015b); writing assessments to help expand NCO communications skills (Tice 2015a); and initiatives to increase civilian schooling credits for Army PME courses (Tan 2014). The expanding education programs reflect the Army’s goal to “make, train

and educate our leaders to be agile and adaptive in a changing world” (Command Sergeant Major Dennis Defreese quoted in Tan 2014).

The Army’s PME-system is a tier-based program. Army service members attend schools according to their rank, and each level of professional development builds on previous knowledge. In between major PME courses that require physical attendance, service members complete Structured Self Development (SSD) modules, which are online classes that work as preparatory and supplemental phases within the PME system. PME courses are constantly improving, and the Army recently adopted a new model of instruction called *The U.S. Army Learning Concept for 2015* (DA 2011). It incorporates experiential learning methods, which facilitate better comprehension and critical-thinking skills by fully immersing students in interactive classroom environments. The Army prides itself on its ability to produce critical thinkers, and after conducting several recent studies, it is taking steps to increase its ability to do so.¹¹⁸ As Fischer, Spiker, and Riedel (2008, v) stated, “advanced training in critical thinking (CT) is needed for adult populations in many fields of work. Not surprisingly, the United States military is at the forefront of efforts to promote and improve thinking skills.”

The Army’s focus, however, is on a certain type of critical thinking. It is assessing “potential usefulness of training critical thinking skills for use on the battlefield” (Cohen, Salas, and Riedel 2002, iv). With its intended use for navigating battlefield complexities and in mission development and mission planning (MDMP), Army critical thinking is almost exclusively focused on problem solving. Rarely do soldiers get exposed to logical fallacies or errors in reasoning. If they do, they are most likely mid-grade officers. When

118. See Fischer, Spiker, and Riedel (2008, 2009a, 2009b), Straus et al. (2013), and Cohen, Salas, and Riedel (2002).

mid-grade officers receive advanced MDMP training, they learn about creating and testing hypotheses, some of the cognitive processes involved in making decisions, and a “what if” approach to critical thinking. All soldiers learn MDMP, however. It is essential to military operations. At every level of PME, soldiers use their operational knowledge and experience to develop courses of action, identify contingencies, and analyze battlefield environments, threats, and problems. They are encouraged to “think outside of the box,” which could easily be translated simply as “be creative.” Colonel (retired) Stephen Gerras, PhD (2008), suggested that Army leaders should be taught “the knowledge, skills, and terminology associated with critical thinking” (26). At least one course has adopted this approach by teaching mid-grade officers the Linda Elder and Richard Paul “Critical Thinking Model” and “Elements of Thought” shown in Fig. 3. The course also briefly discusses pitfalls in thinking and logical fallacies. This is a huge step in the right direction. According to the research conducted for this thesis, however, at no point do NCOs receive this type of training in the PME system for enlisted personnel. The only formal critical-thinking training the Army offers appears to begin at the mid-grade level in officer-specific PME.¹¹⁹

119. Additionally, some Army instructor courses do briefly cover critical-thinking training, but with little to no focus on logical fallacies.

Fig. 3: Foundation for Critical Thinking Tools
 Source: Undisclosed Army mid-grade officer PME course.

Today’s Army focuses heavily on modern battlefield complexity.¹²⁰ The Army seeks to “win in a complex world” by incorporating advances in cognitive, behavioral, and learning sciences that will improve critical thinking (DA 2014c). According to the Army’s *Globally Responsive Sustainment* plan (CASC 2013), “the principal imperative in training our sustainment leaders for the future ... is to ensure that the training environment replicates the future OE [operational environment] as fully as possible” (15). Battlefield-focused training has always been a staple of Army readiness, but today’s battlefield offers especially unique challenges. Some enemies are simply bad ideas. Conspiracist propaganda is more widespread and than ever before, and the Internet allows conspiracy-theory-based memes to propagate at astounding speeds. According to counterinsurgency warfare theorist David Galula (2006):

The insurgent, having no responsibility, is free to use every trick; if necessary he can lie, cheat, exaggerate. He is not obligated to prove; he is judged by what he promises, not by what he does. Consequently, propaganda is a powerful weapon for him. With no positive policy but with good propaganda, the insurgent may still win. (9)

120. See DA (2012b, 2013, 2014a, 2014b, 2014c), CASC (2013), and CAL (2012).

Today, conspiracism is both the insurgent and the propaganda. It uses every trick in the book and is judged not by what it promises but by how it feels. With unrestricted freedom of movement, it has access to nearly every mind. Most people are not trained to fight against it.

Bartlett and Miller (2010, 5) suggested that “fighting the ideology of extremist groups ... should also target the myths, lies, and conspiracies that are part of it.” They suggest making government more transparent and “investing more resources in enabling people to think critically.” Furthermore, “government intervention should teach young people to critically assess propaganda, lies, and half-truths themselves” (38). As both a government institution and a target for extremist recruitment, the US Army should take the lead in developing an education-based approach for combating conspiracism.

Already a proponent of critical thinking and education, the Army has a robust system in place to provide its service members with additional skills to lessen their vulnerability to conspiracism-based extremist propaganda. Focused additions to PME course material—combined with enhancing critical-thinking training—could drastically improve the Army’s education system, create more and better critical thinkers, and further professionalize the force. According to a recent DOD (2012a, 40) demographics report, over 78% of active-duty military personnel do not possess a degree higher than a high school diploma (See Fig. 4). High school curricula sharply vary. Many soldiers enter the Army with very little working knowledge of the subjects that conspiracy theories frequently exploit or misconstrue. Some soldiers have never been exposed to the essential information required to build a framework in which effective critical-thinking skills can be used. They may be exceptional critical thinkers but without that crucial framework,

soldiers remain vulnerable to the power of conspiracism. Additionally, 50 to 60 percent of soldiers serve only one or two tours of duty (Tan 2014). With formal critical thinking focused exclusively on officers—and beginning only at the mid-grade level—most Army personnel will never be exposed to actual instruction on how to think critically. They will use their skills to solve problems and “think outside of the box.” They will not be equipped to work through fallacious reasoning. They will, however, learn tactics techniques and procedures that could provide extremist groups with dangerous capabilities—and that process begins on day one of basic training.

Fig. 4: Military Education Level of Active Duty Members.
 Source: DOD (2012a, 40)

The Army does have a system in place to address extremist recruitment and targeting. The Army’s Threat Awareness and Reporting Program (TARP) is an annual training requirement for all service members. TARP training consists of web-based modules and classroom instruction taught by specially trained instructors. The purpose of

TARP is to make soldiers aware of DOD-focused extremist targeting and recruitment. It also ensures that all soldiers know how and when to report suspicious or extremist activity. TARP is effective for its intended purpose and should not be changed to address conspiracy theories. Officially addressing the theories directly will be ineffective and counterproductive. Individual conspiracy theories should never be overtly attacked.

Educating the Force: Developing a New Approach

After analyzing conspiracism and its relationship to extremist ideologies, this paper suggests that the Army should view conspiracism as a valid and significant threat. This research suggests that the Army should develop a strategy to include non-military-specific coursework into its PME. It should also substantially enhance its critical-thinking training. As soldiers at all levels and ranks take on increased levels of responsibility (DA 2013; DA 2014a, 2014c; CASC 2013), providing this type of education will result in secondary benefits. It will produce soldiers who are more capable of interfacing with citizens, leaders, and service members in the international community. It will create reasoning, problem-solving critical thinkers better able to use their skills in effective ways beyond MDMP and the “battlefield.”¹²¹ It will better educate and professionalize the force as a whole.

Designing a full, working strategy to apply an education-based approach for combating conspiracism is beyond the scope of this thesis. It does, however, provide the following crucial suggestions for strategy development:

121. As Professor Nicholas Murray, PhD (2014), of the US Army Command and Staff College pointed out, some people claim that encouraging too much critical thinking may cause dissension among the ranks because low-ranking soldiers might begin to question their commanders. More critical thinking may produce the opposite effect, however, as soldiers may begin to better understand their commanders’ decisions or be able to better formulate reasonable contingency plans or counterarguments that might better contribute to command decisions.

- Update current critical-thinking training to include instruction on logical fallacies.
- Incorporate formal critical-thinking training at the lowest levels of Army PME.
- Develop annual web-based critical-thinking training akin to current programs for Operational Security (OPSEC) and TARP.
- Update Army PME to include basic courses in subjects such as political science, international relations theory, economics, history, and government administration.
- Analyze popular conspiracy theories and develop training focused on commonly misunderstood or misrepresented institutions, such as the FED, UN, and WTO.

These additions to Army education would provide soldiers with the *skills* and the *framework* they need to work through the faulty logic used in conspiracy-theory-based propaganda. Such enhancements would simultaneously better educate the overall force while helping to mitigate the formation of a conspiracist mentality that can lead to a Manichean worldview and possible violent extremism.

CHAPTER 7: CONCLUSION

Conspiracy theories are cosmopolitan and democratic: nearly everyone plays the antagonist at some point. Domestic villains include or come from nearly every religion, political party/ideology, level and department of government. Foreign villains come from all over the globe. (Uscinski, Parent, and Torres 2011, 26)

The “root causes” of extremism and terrorism come in many forms. Economic, social, religious, and political pressures are usually major contributing factors (CJES 2010, 1.25; Mason 2006, v). So is conspiracism. Most people and institutions tend to largely discount the important role that conspiracy theories often play in the formation of extremist ideologies. They associate conspiracy theories with tin foil hats and UFOs rather than ammonium nitrate bombs and suicide vests. Conspiracism is just one of many reasons people use to justify violent behavior, but it is often *the* reason that can tie all of the others together.

According to Professor Michael Barkun, PhD (2003, 183), “conspiracism developed over the last decade of the twentieth century into the connective tissue binding together a heterogeneous set of beliefs.” Professor Robert Goldberg, PhD (2001, 21), said Americans entered the twenty-first century “haunted by, yet attached to, their conspiracy theory fears.” Today, conspiracy theories permeate the Internet and the media. They are commonly found in the plots of movies, television shows, and popular literature. Most people have come to expect nefarious criminals or government agencies to be revealed as conspiratorial masterminds at the conclusion of their favorite works of fiction. Many people expect the same when reading the daily news. The conspiracist mentality is no longer reserved for the paranoid or the delusional. It has become an integral aspect of popular culture.

As Chapter 5 explained, humans form conspiracy theories as part of natural processes. We look for patterns and meaning in everything we do. As Linda Elder and Richard Paul (2008a, 3) stated, “the human mind is a marvelous set of structures and systems. It is a center of consciousness and action. It forms a unique identity. It creates a view of the world.” Sometimes that view is a product of apophenia—false pattern recognition—that emerges when we assign meaning where there is none. As a form of apophenia, conspiracy theories can profoundly affect a person’s worldview. They may even come to define it. The resultant conspiracism both creates and reinforces a Manichean perspective, which paints the world in black and white, and it offers simplistic explanations for complex problems. According to Elder and Paul (2009, 4–5), “all reasoning is an attempt to figure something out, to settle some question, to solve some problem. ... All reasoning leads somewhere or has implications and consequences.” Conspiracy theories are attempts to “figure out” the *cui bono* question, and the answers they provide can lead believers to drastic conclusions with dangerous consequences. As philosopher Avital Ronell, PhD, said in the documentary *Examined Life* (2008, 11:05–11:10), “the minute you think you know the ‘other,’ you’re ready to kill them.”

Conspiracism is common across the spectrum of extremist ideologies. In fact, it can become the conspiracist pidgin that unites disparate groups toward common goals. The conspiracy theories that such groups propagate become “radicalizing multipliers” that aid in recruitment and push extremists in more violent directions (Bartlett and Miller 2010). They demonize the “other,” objectify the “hidden hand” of intentionality, and scapegoat the world’s problems onto individual people, groups, institutions, or governments. Chapter 3 demonstrated the radicalizing power of conspiracism by

detailing the Patriot movement's violent conspiracy-theory-laced history from the anti-communist hysteria of the early Cold War to the anti-government terrorism that followed it. The Patriots emerged in response to changing political and social environments and in reaction to fear. Conspiracism made them more extreme. Today, new conspiracy theories have caused their numbers to resurge. Nationwide, Patriot militias train in military tactics, patrol the borders, and once again prepare for war. Recent standoffs with government agents have demonstrated their willingness—perhaps eagerness—for armed “resistance,” and they are actively seeking new recruits. So are terrorist groups across the globe. Conspiracism is one of their most effective weapons.

Conspiracy theories should be taken seriously. They are present in every society and prevalent in most extremist ideologies. In America, a propensity to accept Manichean perspectives, a widespread belief in conspiracy theories, and a culture permeated with conspiracist ideation that traverses both the realms of fact and fiction, leaves many—if not most—Americans vulnerable to conspiracy-theory-based extremist propaganda. A number of “societal-level forces” play a large role in popularizing conspiracy theories (Leman and Cinnirella 2013, 8), but education may be the key to combating their effects. As Chapter 6 explained, conspiracism results from mental shortcuts that lead to bad decisions. Those decisions, however, may be perfectly rational in relation to limited information. Conspiracy-theory-based propaganda uses fallacious reasoning to create the appearance of rationality. It exploits half-truths and relies on bad evidence to form convincing—but unsound—arguments. Critical thinking can be used to dismantle the flawed logic inherent to such argumentation, but critical thinking requires an intellectual

framework in order to be effective. And critical thinking itself can be improved through training (Fischer, Spiker, and Riedel 2009a).

As Professor Robert Sapolsky, PhD (2010a), explained, people tend to think in categories, which makes it easier for them to deal with the facts. Conspiracists categorize events according to whatever knowledge they have at their disposal, and conspiracy theories often provide “facts” based on misconstrued ideas about historical, political and social realities. For education to be effective it must provide a relevant base of knowledge in which new and better categorical thinking can occur. The conspiracist must acquire a frame of reference in which to think critically. His reality must become more complex, and conspiracy theories must make the transition from fact to fiction. The false patterns have to stop making sense.

This thesis proposes an education-based approach for combating conspiracism and suggests that the US Army should take the lead in implementing such a strategy. As Chapter 4 demonstrated, military veterans have filled leadership and violent roles throughout the history of the Patriot movement. The trend continues today. Furthermore, many extremist groups are focusing their recruitment strategies on veterans who can provide substantial skills and expertise to potentially dangerous movements. The conspiracy-theory-based propaganda such groups propagate can convince those veterans to put those skills and expertise to use. Enhancements to critical-thinking training and additions to professional development courses, however, may be effective in mitigating extremist recruitment within the military’s ranks. They will definitely better educate the overall force.

As Professor George Michael, PhD (2006, 13), said, “virtually all terrorists come from the ranks of extremists, most extremists are not terrorists,” but “political extremism often serves as an incubator for future terrorism.” Similarly, conspiracism often serves as an incubator for extremism, and it can easily become justification for terrorism. It is more than just tin foil hats. It is a worldview, and one that can be dangerous. Everyone is at risk. We are all natural conspiracy theorists, and we are very good at convincing ourselves that our theories are true. Education can help us to defeat that self-deception, not by teaching us *what* to think but rather *how* to think. It can enable us to make better-informed decisions about what we should or should not believe—and how we should react to what we decide.

Suggestions for Further Research

This thesis discussed a number of topics spanning multiple disciplines. Further research could add value to the information, conclusions, and suggestions presented in this paper.

The author suggests the following research questions for additional study:

- Are military veterans who join extremist organizations more likely to fill leadership roles or the most violent positions within such groups? Are military veterans especially prone to conspiratorial thinking?
- How can the Army—or the military in general—best incorporate the recommended subjects into its professional development programs?
- How can the Army—or the military in general—most effectively and efficiently enhance its critical-thinking training, and how can it best train students on logical fallacies?
- What types of educational training are most effective at defeating conspiracy-theory-based propaganda?
- Would a similar education-based approach be an effective tool in other critical areas, such as prison counter-radicalization programs or counterterrorism strategies?

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